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The Etymology of the Gymnophiona of the World

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Abstract

The etymologies of the generic names and specific epithets of all the Gymnophiona described between 1758 and 2023 are presented, pinpointing their current taxonomic standing. Each reference includes illuminating excerpts from the original descriptions, or from the directly transcribed original etymology, to shed light on the nomenclatural origins.

Key words: Amphibia, Gymnophiona, Scientific names, Etymology

INTRODUCTION:

This contribution delves into the etymology of the Gymnophiona (caecilians) of the world, spanning from *Caecilia tentaculata*, the first of two caecilian species described by Linnaeus in 1758, to *Caecilia wilkinsoni*, the latest name published by Fernández-Roldán & Lynch, on April 20,

2023. As highlighted in the Etymologies of Brazilian Amphibians (Lavilla et al., 2022), the main focus of this text is on the lexical analysis and not a systematic or exhaustive synonym list (though necessarily informed by them). Likewise, it doesn't claim to be a nomenclatural-work adhering to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN, 1999). The primary source for taxa was the American Museum of Natural History's Amphibian Species of the World Website (Frost, 2024) for recent species and Santos *et al.* (2020) for the fossils, supplemented by in-depth examination of each original description (see aforementioned web-page and publication for the bibliographic references).

To the greatest extent possible, each analyzed term is accompanied by:

- Its constituent word(s) and language of origin:

- A.** Arawak. Arawak family of languages. Spoken in Venezuela, Guyana, Suriname, French Guiana, and Brazil. They are also spoken in several Caribbean islands, including Trinidad and Tobago, Barbados, Jamaica, and the Dominican Republic.
- B.** Bantu. Bantu family of languages, branch of the larger Niger-Congo family of languages. Large group of over 500 languages spoken in Tanzania, Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Zambia, Malawi, Zimbabwe, Mozambique, Angola, and South Africa.
- C.** Chinese. Sino-Tibetan family of languages. Spoken primarily in China, Taiwan, and Singapore.
- Ch.** Chocó. Part of the larger Chibchan family of languages. Spoken in parts of Colombia and Panama, particularly in the Chocó-Darién region.
- Ce.** Cebuan. Austronesian family of languages. Spoken in the central Visayas region (Cebu, Bohol, and parts of Leyte, Samar, and Negros), Philippines.
- D.** Darlong or Dalong. Part of the Sino-Tibetan language family, and possibly the Kuki-Chin sub-group of the Tibeto-Burman language family. Spoken in the Kailashahar and Kamalpur subdivisions of North Tripura district, Tripura, as well as Cachar district, Assam, India
- E.** English. West Germanic branch of the Germanic family of languages. Spoken as an official language in many countries, widely used as a second language and *lingua franca* around the world.
- F.** French. Romance family of language. Spoken as a first language primarily in France, Belgium, Switzerland, Canada, and several African countries. Also widely spoken as a second language in many countries around the world, particularly in former French colonies.
- Fu.** Fula (a.k.a. Fulani or Pulaar). Niger-Congo family of languages. Spoken by the Fula people in West and Central Africa.
- G.** Greek. Indo-European family of languages. Spoken in the Balkans and Mediterranean regions for over three millennia. Official language of Greece and Cyprus.
- Ga.** Garo. Tibeto-Burman language (Bodo-Naga Section). Spoken in the Northeast Indian states of Meghalaya, Assam, and Tripura, and in some areas of neighboring Bangladesh.
- Ge.** German. West Germanic branch of the Germanic family of languages. Spoken primarily in Germany, Austria, Switzerland, and Liechtenstein.
- In?** Unspecified Indian dialect or language.
- K.** Konkani. Indo-Aryan language. Spoken primarily in the Indian states of Goa, Karnataka, and Maharashtra, as well as in some parts of Kerala and Gujarat.
- Kh.** Khmer. Austroasiatic language family. Spoken in Cambodia.
- L.** Latin and Neo-Latin. Italic branch of the Indo-European language family. Official language of Vatican City.
- La.** Lao. Tai-Kadai language family. Spoken primarily in Laos, but also in Thailand, Cambodia, and Vietnam.

- M.** Marathi. Indo-Aryan language family. Spoken in western and central India, from north of Mumbai down the western coast past Goa and eastward across the Deccan.
- Ma.** Malayan (a.k.a. Bahasa Melayu or Melayu). Austronesian family of languages. Spoken in Malaysia, Brunei, and Indonesia, and is also spoken in Singapore, southern Thailand, and the Philippines.
- Mk.** Makushi (a. k. a. Macushi, Makusi, Macuxi, Macusi, Macussi, Teweya, or Teueia). Carib language family. Spoken in Brazil, Guyana, and Venezuela.
- P.** Portuguese. Romance language. Spoken in Portugal, Brazil, Angola, Mozambique, Guinea-Bissau, Cape Verde, São Tomé and Príncipe, and East Timor.
- Q.** Quechua (a.k.a. Quichua, Kichwa, Runasimi). Quechuan language family. Spoken primarily in the Andean region of South America, including parts of Peru, Bolivia, Ecuador, Colombia, Argentina, and Chile.
- S.** Spanish. Romance language. Spoken in Spain and in many countries throughout the Americas, as well as in Equatorial Guinea, the Philippines, and parts of North Africa.
- Sa.** Sanskrit. Ancient Indo-European language. Primarily used as a sacred and literary language in India.
- Sc.** Seychellois creole (a.k.a. Seselwa or kreol). Mix of African languages like Malagasy and Swahili, with large French influences. Spoken in the Republic of the Seychelles.
- Sw.** Swahili. Bantu family of languages, branch of the larger Niger-Congo family of languages. Spoken in Kenya, Tanzania, Uganda, and the Democratic Republic of Congo.
- T.** Tupí. Tupí-Guaraní language family. After the European conquest, *lingua franca* between natives and Portuguese traders, missionaries, adventurers, and administrators. Spoken in Brazil and neighboring countries of South America.
- Ta.** Tanimuka (a.k.a. Tanimuca-Retuarã and Letuama). Tucanoan language spoken in Colombia. Probably of an Arawakan origin.
- Tm.** Tamil. Dravidian language. Spoken primarily in the Indian state of Tamil Nadu, as well as in parts of Sri Lanka, Singapore, and Malaysia.
- Th.** Thai. Tai-Kadai language. Spoken in Thailand, Laos, and Cambodia, as well as by Thai communities around the world.
- V.** Vietnamese. Austroasiatic language family. Spoken in Vietnam and in Vietnamese diaspora communities.

- A relevant excerpt from the original description supporting the chosen etymology (or its transcription, if explicitly stated).
- The original combination in which it was used.
- Current synonym, if applicable.
- Question marks [?] prior to the name indicate undefined original language; at the end of the etymologies reflect that there are no further data associated with the origin or meaning of the name in the original description.

The most used sources to elucidate the origin of names were Brown's lexicon (1954), as a first step towards understanding names in Latin and Greek. For Greek, Bailly (1895), Beekes & Van Beek (2010), Borrer (1960), Diggle et al. (2021) and Lidell & Scott (1996); Latin sources include the dictionaries by Borrer (1960), De Vaan (2008) and Glare (2012). Additionally, some names were identified based on Beolens *et al.* (2013), as well as various online dictionaries for less widely spoken languages

ETYMOLOGIES

abitaguae: S. [Cerros de] Abitagua, mountain in Pastaza, Ecuador; in turn from Q. *abitagua*, burning or hot mountain. *Caecilia abitaguae* Dunn, 1942. ["...Type locality: Abitagua, Oriente, Ecuador, 1100 m. elevation..."].

Abranchia: G. a- (α-), not, without, negative, privative + G. *branchia* (βράγχια), gills. *Abranchia* Hogg, 1838. ["...Branchial apparatus none..."]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

acuminatus: L. *acuminatus*, sharp, pointed, tapering. *Ichthyophis acuminatus* Taylor, 1960. ["...*acuminatus* (Latin) = pointed, referring to the snout..."].

Adélobatraciens: G. *adelos* (ἀ-δηλος), unseen, unknown, obscure + F. *batraciens*, from G. *batrachos* (βάτραχος), frog. *Adélobatraciens* Gouriet, 1868. ["...*dans le sens vertical on aura la division en Batraciens par excellence ou Eubatraciens et en Batraciens moins évidents ou Adélobatraciens, le tout formant deux séries parallèles dans les deux sens...*"]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

africanus: L. *africanus*, African; from, of Africa. *Uraeotyphlus africanus* Boulenger, 1882. [“... West Africa...”]. In the synonymy of *Geotrypetes seraphini* (Duméril, 1859).

Afrocaecilia: L. *Afrum*, African; of, connected with Africa + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Afrocaecilia* Taylor, 1968. [“... East Africa...”]. Same root in *Afrocaeciliiti* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986. In the synonymy of *Boulengerula* Tornier, 1896.

albiceps: L. *albus*, white (color) + L. *-ceps*, from L. *caput*, head. *Dermophis albiceps* Boulenger, 1882. [“...Blackish grey, the head white...”]. Today *Microcaecilia albiceps* (Boulenger, 1882).

albiventris: L. *albus*, white, pale + L. *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly. *Caecilia albiventris* Daudin, 1803. [“...cum abdomine ex albo flavescente variegato...”].

alcocki: Alcock + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Chikila alcocki* Kamei, Gower, Wilkinson & Biju, 2013. Honoring Alfred William Alcock (1859-1933), former Superintendent of the Indian Museum.

alfredi: Alfred + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis alfredi* Mathew & Sen, 2009. Honoring J. R. B. Alfred (?), former Director of the Zoological Survey of India.

alternans: L. *alternus*, do by turns, vary; alternate. *Hypogeophis alternans* Stejneger, 1893. [“...the complete primary rings alternate with secondary rings broadly interrupted on the dorsal and ventral lines...”]. Today *Grandisonia alternans* (Stejneger, 1893).

amazops: S., P. Amazonas, a South American river, state and city [in turn, from G. *Amazón* (Ἀμαζών), a woman warrior of the classic world] + G. *ops* (ὄψ), eye. (1) *Amazops* Wilkinson, Reynolds & Jacobs, 2021. [“...The name is a portmanteau word combining reference to the Amazonian provenance of the type and only known species and the distinctive topological relationships of its eye and orbit, particularly the contribution of the squamosal to the bony margin of the orbit, which is unknown in any other rhinatrematid...”). (2) *Amazops amazops* Wilkinson, Reynolds & Jacobs, 2021. [“...Etymology. As for the genus...”].

Amblyopes: G. *amblyopos* (ἀμβλυπόσ), dim-sighted. *Amblyopes* Goldfuss, 1820. [“...Wurmschlangen...”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

Amphiumophis: G. *amphi* (ἀμφί), on both or all sides + G. *uma* (ὔμα), apocope of πνεῦμα, breath + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Amphiumophis* Werner, 1901. [? Probably meaning *Amphiu-* *ma*-like snake, being *Amphiu-* *ma* a genus of aquatic salamander due to Garden, 1821]. In the synonymy of *Caecilia* Linnaeus, 1758.

andicola: S. Andes, South American mountain range [in turn, from ? Andes, a pre-Hispanic people in the Jauja region (Junín, Peru) that gave the mountain range its name] + L. *-cola*, dwelling in, inhabiting, living among. *Amphiumophis andicola* Werner, 1901. [“...Ein Exemplar ...vom Chanchamayo...” (a province in Junin Department, Peru)]. In the synonymy of *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758.

angeli: Angel L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Geotrypetes angeli* Parker, 1936. Honoring Fernand Angel (1881-1950), French herpetologist.

anguillaformis: L. *anguillaformis*, eel-shaped. *Typhlonectes anguillaformis* Taylor, 1968. [“...Low dermal “fin” visible from the greater part of body length...”]. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

Anguinea: L. *anguis*, a serpent, snake + L. *-ea*, suffix indicating quality of. *Anguinea* Leunis, 1860. [“...Schleichenlurche...”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

angusticeps: L. *angustus*, narrow, steep + L. *-iceps*, from L. *caput*, head. *Hypogeophis angusticeps* Parker, 1941. [“...is recognizable by its much smaller head...”]. In the synonymy of *Grandisonia larvata* (Ahl, 1934).

annulata: L. *annulatus*, provided with a ring, ringed; fitted with a fetter, fettered (in turn, *annulatus* derives from L. *annuus*, of the year, annual). *Caecilia annulata* Mikan, 1822. [“...corpore crasso, nigra, annulis albo-marginatis...”]. Today *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1822).

antioquiaensis: S. Antioquia, one of the 32 departments of Colombia (in turn, a toponym of doubtful origin, probably derived from

Ἀντιόχεια, Greek name of a city in present-day Syria that is mentioned several times in the New Testament of the Bible) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Caecilia antioquiaensis* Taylor, 1968. [“...Valdivia, Antioquia...”].

Aphanobranchiata: G. *aphanes* (ἀφανής), unseen, invisible, viewless + G. *branchia* (βράγχια), gills. Aphanobranchiata Leuckart, 1840. [“...Schwindkiemet...”]. In the synonymy of Gymnophiona.

Apoda: G. *apous* (ἄπους), without foot. Apoda Oppel, 1811 [“...pedibus carens...”]. In the synonymy of Gymnophiona.

Apodops: G. *apodos* (ἄποδος) out of tune + G. *ops* (ὄψ), the eye or face. *Apodops* Estes & Wake, 1972. [“...Greek *apodos*, out of tune; *ops*, face: refers to the resemblance to an African genus of this South American fossil...”].

aprix: G. *aprix* (ἀπρίξ), with a tight grasp, tightly. *Caecilia aprix* Fernández-Roldán & Rueda-Almonacid, 2022. [“...The specific epithet is Greek, meaning ‘with closed teeth’ or ‘with fast, tight teeth’. The name seems to fit this species because its inner mandibular series consists of four short,

thick, pointed teeth on each side of the mouth that are situated very close to one another...”].

arii: Ari + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Chthonerpeton arii* Cascon & Lima-Verde, 1994. Honoring Ari Santiago Lima-Verde, Brazilian physician.

armata: L. *armata*, defensively armed, armor clad. *Caecilia armata* Dunn, 1942. [“...This remarkable form has the hind half of the body with bony scales...”].

asplenius: G. *a-* (α-), privative particle + G. *splenion* (σπληνίον), splenial (referring to the splenial bone). *Ichthyophis asplenius* Taylor, 1965. [“...no splenial teeth in transformed specimens...”].

atelolepis: G. *ateles* (ατελής), imperfect + G. *lepis* (λεπίς), scales (on animals). *Caecilia atelolepis* Fernández-Roldán, Lynch & Medina-Rangel, 2023. [“...The specific epithet is a combination of the Greek words *atelos* and *lepis*, meaning imperfect or unaccomplished scales. The name is given in reference to the poorly developed dermal scales of this species, which can be absent or very small, irregularly shaped, folded, and

mostly restricted to the terminal portion of the body...”].

Atretochoana: *G. a-tretos* (α-τρητος), imperforate + *G. choane* (χοάνη), funnel or tube, choana. *Atretochoana* Nussbaum & Wilkinson, 1995. [“...typhlonectid caecilians with sealed choanae, no lungs, no no pulmonary blood vessels..”].

atricollaris: *L. atri*, from *L. ater*, black, dark; dark-colored + *L. collaris*, of, pertaining to, belonging to the neck. *Ichthyophis atricollaris* Taylor, 1965. [“...neck nearly uniformly dark above and below, the collars only dimly indicated...”].

attenuata, attenuatus: *L. attenuata*, -us, to make thin, make slender, wear away, dilute, rarefy, attenuate. (1) *Caecilia attenuata* Taylor, 1968. [“...A very slender form...”]. (2) *Scolecophorus attenuatus* Barbour & Loveridge, 1928. [“...Habit much more slender...”]. In the synonymy of *Scolecophorus uluguruensis* Barbour & Loveridge, 1928.

balboai: Balboa + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Dermophis balboai* Taylor, 1968. Without

mention in the original description, probably Honoring Vasco Núñez de Balboa (1475–1519), the first European to cross the isthmus of Panamá. In the synonymy of *Dermophis glandulosus* Taylor, 1955.

bannanica: *C. Banna*, apocope of Xishuangbanna, autonomous prefecture for Dai people in the extreme south of Yunnan Province, China + *L. -ica*, suffix used to indicate possession or association with something. *Ichthyophis bannanica* Yang, 1984. [“...云南西双版纳勐腊县城郊，海拔600米...” (Outskirts of Mengla County, Xishuangbanna, Yunnan, 600 meters above sea level)...”]. In the synonymy of *Ichthyophis kohtaoensis* Taylor, 1960.

bassleri: Bassler + *L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia bassleri* Dunn, 1942. Honoring Harvey Bassler (1883–1950), US American geologist and herpetologist. Today *Osaecilia bassleri* (Dunn, 1942).

Batrachophides: *G. batrachos* (βάτραχος), frog + *Gr. ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Batrachophides* Latreille, 1825. [?]. Same root in *Batrachophides* Bonaparte, 1831, *Batrachophidii*

Bonaparte, 1832, Batrachopidii — Bonaparte, 1839 (incorrect subsequent spelling), Batracophidii Bonaparte, 1838 (incorrect subsequent spelling), Batrachophid-ia Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

battersbyi: Battersby + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Indotyphlus battersbyi* Taylor, 1960. Honoring James Clarence Battersby (1901–1993), British herpetologist.

Bdellophis: G. *bdella* (βδέλλα), blood-sucking creature, leech + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Bdellophis* Boulenger, 1895. [“... Body much flattened...”]. In the synonymy of *Scolecormorphus* Boulenger, 1883.

beddomei: Beddome + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis beddomei* Peters, 1880. Honoring Colonel Richard Henry Beddome (1830–1911), British officer in India and naturalist.

benjii: Benji + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis benjii* Lalremsanga, Purkayastha, Biakzuala, Mathipi, Muansanga &

Hmar, 2021. Honoring the memory of Benjamin Lalremsanga (1988–2020), nephew of the first author.

bernisi: Bernis + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis bernisi* Salvador, 1975. Honoring Francisco Bernis Madrazo (1916–2003), Spanish ornithologist.

biangularis: L. *bi*, two, twice; double; having two + L. *angularis*, having angles or corners. *Ichthyophis biangularis* Taylor, 1965. [“...transverse folds distinctly angular above as below, throughout most of body...”].

bicolor: L. *bicolor*, of two colors. *Epicrionops bicolor* Boulenger, 1883. [“...Dark brown; a broad yellow band along each side of the belly, nearly as broad as the interspace, commencing from the mouth, uniting in front of the vent, and occupying the lower half of the tail...”].

billitonensis: E. Billiton (Palau Belitung in Malay), island in Karimata Strait (probably from *Ma. belat*, island, or *betung*, sand) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis billitonensis* Taylor, 1965. [“...The species is named

for its place of origin, the island of Billiton situated in the northern part of the Java Sea, between Sumatra, Borneo, and Java...”].

bivittata: L. *bi*, two + L. *vittata*, wearing or carrying a ritual band or ribbon. *Caecilia bivittata* Guérin-Méneville, 1838. [?]. Today *Rhinatrema bivittatum* (Guérin-Méneville, 1838).

bokermanni: Bokermann + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia bokermanni* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Werner Carl August Bokermann (1929–1995), Brazilian herpetologist.

bombayensis: E. Bombay, probably derived from Sa. Mumbadevi, a Hindu deity; it is also suggested that it is a corruption of Portuguese Boa Bahia (good bay) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis bombayensis* Taylor, 1960. [“...Bombay + *ensis* = place, locality, country...”]. Today *Uraeotyphlus bombayensis* (Taylor, 1960).

bornmülleri: Bornmüller + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Herpele bornmülleri* Werner, 1899. Honoring Joseph Friedrich Nicolaus

Bornmüller (1862–1948), German botanist. Today *Crotaphatrema bornmuelleri* (Werner, 1899).

boulengeri: Boulenger + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Boulengerula boulengeri* Tornier, 1896. Honoring George Albert Boulenger (1858–1937), Belgian-British herpetologist.

Boulengerula: Boulenger + L. *-ula*, diminutive suffix. *Boulengerula* Tornier, 1896. See *boulengeri*.

braestrupi: Bræstrup + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Chthonerpeton braestrupi* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Frits Wimpffen Bræstrup (1906–1999), Danish zoologist.

brasiliensis, braziliensis: P. Brasil, South American country (in turn, from P. pau de brasa or pau brasil) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Gymnopsis braziliensis* Dunn, 1945. [“...Four caecilians from Brazil, recently sent me for identification by Mr. C. M. Bogert, represent an undescribed species of the genus *Gymnopsis* and add that genus to the fauna of Brazil...”]. Today *Brasilotyphlus braziliensis* (Dunn, 1945). (2) *Siphon-*

nops brasiliensis Lütken, 1851. [...Det beskrevne Exemplar hidrører fra Brasilien og er sendt til Europa af Dr. Langgaard. Da denne nye Art synes i det sydlige Brasilien at repræsentere den samme Grundform indenfor Slægten Siphonops som *S. mexicanus* i Central-Amerika, er Artsnavnet valgt i Overeensstemmelse dermed..."]. Today *Luetkenotyphlus brasiliensis* (Lütken, 1852).

Brasilotyphlus: P. Brasil, South American country (in turn, from P. pau de brasa or pau brasil) + G. *typhlos* (τυφλος), blind. *Brasilotyphlus* Taylor, 1968. [...Type of genus: *Gymnophis braziliensis* Dunn..."]. Same root in *Brasilotyphlili* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986.

brevirostris: L. *brevis*, short, little, small + L. *rostris*, beak, snout. *Siphonops brevirostris* Peters, 1874. [...Der Kopf hat eine ähnliche Gestalt, wie bei *S. indistinctus*, aber die Schnauze ragt viel weniger über die Maulöffnung hervor, als bei dieser oder einer anderen der bekannten Siphonops-Arten..."]. In the synonymy of *Schistometopum thomense* (Bocage, 1873).

brevis: L. *brevis*, short, little, small. *Hypogeophis brevis* Boulenger, 1911. [...Body very short, its diameter 14 or 15 times in the total length..."].

buckleyi: Buckley + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia buckleyi* Boulenger, 1884. Honoring Clarence Buckley, English professional collector active in Ecuador, Bolivia, and possibly Colombia during the late 1860's and 1870's. In the synonymy of *Caecilia pachynema* Günther, 1859.

butantan: P. Butantan, a district in São Paulo, Brazil, and a biomedical research center founded in 1901, from T. *butantã*, corr. *yby-tantã*, hard, firm ground. *Microcaecilia butantan* Wilkinson, Antoniazzi & Jared, 2015. [...The specific epithet is in honour of the Instituto Butantan, which enabled the discovery of the species through the Butantan na Amazônia (Butantan in Amazon) project..."].

Caecilia: L. *caecilia*, blind-worm, in turn from L. *caecus*, blind. *Caecilia* Linnaeus, 1758. [?]. Same root in *Cecilinia* Rafinesque, 1814, *Caeciliidae* Rafinesque, 1814, *Caeciliadae* Gray, 1825, *Caeciliina* Bonaparte, 1850, and variations of the name.

Caecilita: L. *Caecilia*, caecilian genus due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name) + *-ita*, suffix diminutive. *Caecilita* Wake & Donnelly, 2010. [...The generic epithet refers to the small size of the new caeciliid taxon...].

cardamomensis: E. Cardamom [Mountains], E. for Kh. Krâvanh ជួរភ្នំកាដាម៉ុំ; mountain range in the southwest of Cambodia and Eastern Thailand (refers to *Elettaria cardamomum*: Zingiberaceae; in turn, from G. κάρδαμον, cress) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis cardamomensis* Geissler, Poyarkov, Grismer, Nguyen, An, Neang, Kupfer, Ziegler, Böhme & Müller, 2015. [...We name this new species after the geographic region of its known distribution, the Cardamom Mountains in western Cambodia...].

caribea: L. *caribea*, belonging or related to the Caribbean. In turn, from A. *caribe*, name used to describe the predominant Amerindian ethnicity in the region at the time of the first contact with Europeans at the end of the 15th century, probably meaning strength and bravery. *Caecilia caribea* Dunn, 1942. [...Range. Known only from type locality and from Barranquilla, Colombia...]

carnosum: L. *carnosus*, fleshy; characterized by flesh; consisting of meat; fleshy in color, appearance. *Epicrium carnosum* Beddome, 1870. [...of a uniform bright fleshy color when alive, fading to a reddish brown in spirits...]. Today *Gegeneophis carnosus* (Beddome, 1870).

catlocensis: V. Cat Loc, sector of the present Cat Tien National Park; originally a rhinoceros reserve + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis catlocensis* Geissler, Poyarkov, Grismer, Nguyen, An, Neang, Kupfer, Ziegler, Böhme & Müller, 2015. [...We name this new species after its type locality, the Cat Loc area of the Cat Tien National Park...].

Caudacaecilia: L. *cauda*, tail (animal); extreme part, tail of anything + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Caudacaecilia* Taylor, 1968. [...a tail is present...]. In the synonymy of *Ichthyophis Fitzinger, 1826*.

Celatibranhia: L. *celatus*, concealed, hidden + G. *branchia* (βράγχια), gills. *Celatibranhia* Hogg, 1841. [...Gill-fringes concealed...]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

chaloensis: V. Cha Lo [Village] + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis chaloensis* Geissler, Poyarkov, Grismer, Nguyen, An, Neang, Kupfer, Ziegler, Böhme & Müller, 2015. [“...The specific epithet is in reference to the type locality of the forest near Cha Lo Village, Hoa Son Commune, Minh Hoa District, Quang Binh Province, Central Vietnam...”].

changamwensis: Sw. Changamwe, a suburb of Mombasa (Kenya) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Boulengerula changamwensis* Loveridge, 1932. [“...from Changamwe, near Mombasa, Kenya Colony...”].

Chikila: In? *chikila*, vernacular name for these animals. *Chikila* Kamei, San Mauro, Gower, Van Bocxlaer, Sherratt, Thomas, Babu, Bossuyt, Wilkinson & Biju, 2012. [“...Chikila is a northeast (Meghalaya state) Indian tribal name for the included caecilians...”]. Same root in *Chikilidae* Kamei, San Mauro, Gower, Van Bocxlaer, Sherratt, Thomas, Babu, Bossuyt, Wilkinson & Biju, 2012, *Chikilini* — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021.

Chthonerpeton: G. *chthon* (χθών), earth, soil + G. *erpeton* (ερπετον), reptile. *Chthonerpeton* Peters, 1880. [?].

clarkii: Clark + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gymnophis clarkii* Barbour, 1926. Honoring Herbert Charles Clark (1877–1960), US American physician, first Director of Gorgas Memorial Laboratory, Panama. In the synonymy of *Dermophis mexicanus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

Coecilia: L. *caecilia*, blind-worm, in turn from L. *caecus*, blind. *Coecilia* — Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X”. Previously, Linnaeus (1758) used two alternative original spellings for the limbless amphibians included in SN 10, *Coecilia* on page 196 (corrected to *Caecilia* in the Emendanda after p. 823), and *Caecilia* on page 229. The following year (Linnaeus, 1759: 70; 81), consistently employed the spelling *Caecilia*, but again in SN 12 (Linnaeus, 1766), used both. Same root in *Coeciliae* Müller, 1831, *Coeciliae* Müller, 1832, *Coeciliae* Tschudi, 1838. In the synonymy of *Caecilia* Linnaeus, 1758.

columbianum: L. *Columbia*, Colombia, a South American country named after Christopher Columbus (1451–1506) + L. *-anum*, pertaining to. *Rhinatrema columbianum* Rendahl & Vestergren, 1939. [“...Die betreffenden Sammlu-

ngen stammen aus der Provinz Cauca in Colombia, meistens aus der Umgebung von El Tambo..."]. Today *Epicrionops columbianus* (Rendahl & Vestergren, 1939)

compressicauda: L. *compressus*, constricted, narrow, pressed together + L. *cauda*, tail. *Coecilia compressicauda* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. ["...Extrémité postérieure du tronc assez fortement comprimée à sa partie supérieure ou tectiforme..."]. Today *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

concolor: L. *concolor*, of uniform color throughout. *Rhinatrema concolor* Duméril, 1863. [?]. In the synonymy of *Microcaecilia unicolor* (Duméril, 1863).

confusionis: L. *confusionis*, mingling, mixture, union; confusion, confounding, disorder. *Siphonops confusionis* Taylor, 1968. (Refers to the confusion of this species with *Siphonops*, *Luetkenotyphlus* and *Chthonherpeton*). In the synonymy of *Luetkenotyphlus brasiliensis* (Lütken, 1852).

congoensis: B. Congo (today Democratic Republic of the Congo, from a B. word meaning "mountains") + L. *-ensis*, *belonging to a place*.

Geotrypetes congoensis Taylor, 1968. ["...Mayombe Region, Congo..."]. In the synonymy of *Geotrypetes seraphini* (Duméril, 1859).

convexus: L. *convexus*, arching, arched, vaulted, convex. *Scolecormorphus convexus* Taylor, 1968. ["...convexus = (Latin) arched, in reference to the arch in the anal area..."]. In the synonymy of *Scolecormorphus kirkii* Boulenger, 1883.

cooperi: Cooper + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. (1) *Nectocaecilia cooperi* Taylor, 1970. Honoring Edwin Cooper (1936–), US American biologist and immuno-biology professor. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes natans* (Fischer, 1880). (2) *Praslinia cooperi* Boulenger, 1909. Honoring Sir Clive Forster-Cooper (1880–1947), British zoologist.

Copeotyphlinus: Cope + connective *o* + G. *typhlos* (τυφλος), blind (frequent particle in gymnophiona names) + L. *-inus*, having the nature or condition of). *Copeotyphlinus* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Edward Drinker Cope (1840-1897), US American paleontologist and zoologist. In the synonymy of *Gymnopsis* Peters, 1874.

corpulenta: L. *corpulenta*, corpulent, fat, stout, of a heavy build of body. *Caecilia corpulenta* Taylor, 1968. [“...A large thick-bodied species with a relatively small head...”].

corrugatum: L. *corrugatum*, make wrinkled; corrugate. *Chthonerpeton corrugatum* Taylor, 1968. [“...Skin transversely wrinkled, somewhat more in adults than in young...”]. In the synonymy of *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

costaricense: S., L. *costaricense*, from Costa Rica, a Central American country. *Dermophis costaricense* Taylor, 1955. [“...Of Costa Rica...”].

crassisquama: L. *crassus*, thick, deep; thick coated + L. *squama*, scale. *Caecilia crassisquama* Taylor, 1968. [“...An elongated species lacking secondaries, but with a few thickened (inflexible scales) in the posterior folds...”].

crassus: L. *crassus*, thick, deep; thick coated. *Dermophis crassus* Cope, 1885 “1884”. [“...The most robust species of the genus...”]. In the synonymy of *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1820).

Crotaphatrema: G. *krótaphos* (κρόταφος), side of the forehead, temple + G. -a (-α), privative + G. *trema* (τήμα), that which is created by drilling or piercing, aperture, hole. *Crotaphatrema* Nussbaum, 1985. [“...The generic name is derived from *krotaphos* (Gr.) meaning the temple of the head and *atrema* (Gr.) meaning without holes, in reference to the lack of temporal fossae...”]. Note that G. *átréma* (ἀτρέμα), means without motion or trembling; still, motionless.

Cryptopsophis: G. *krypto* (κρύπτω) hide, cover + G. *ops* (ὄψ) + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Cryptopsophis* Boulenger, 1883. In the characterization of *C. multiplicatus*, the type species of the genus, Boulenger wrote, referring to eyes, [“...latter very indistinct...”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnopsis* Peters, 1874.

cunhai: Cunha + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Typhlonectes cunhai* Cascon, Lima-Verde & Marques 1991. Honoring Osvaldo Rodrigues da Cunha (1928–2011), Brazilian herpetologist. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

danieli: Daniel + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gegeneophis danieli* Giri, Wilkinson & Gower, 2003. Honoring Jivanayakam Cyril Daniel (1927–2011), Indian naturalist.

daribokensis: ? Daribokgre, locality in Meghalaya State, India + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis daribokensis* Mathew & Sen, 2009. [...The species name reflects the name of the locality Daribokgre in East Garo hills district of Meghalaya from where the type materials were collected...].

darlong: D. Darlong (26. 93722 N, 92. 99611 E; 121 m asl), Seijosa, East Kameng district, Arunachal Pradesh, India. The name Darlong is associated also to a language and a small tribe living in Tripura, India. *Chikila darlong* Kamei, Gower, Wilkinson & Biju, 2013. [...The species is named after Darlong where the type series was collected...].

davidi: David + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis davidi* Bhatta, Dinesh, Prashanth, Kulkarni & Radhakrishnan, 2011. Honoring David Gower (1969–), British herpetologist, “...in recognition of his contributions to Indian caecilian studies...”.

degenerata: L. *degeneratus*, degenerate, + L. *-ata*, having the nature of. *Caecilia degenerata* Dunn, 1942. [?].

denhardt: Denhardt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Boulengerula denhardt* Nieden, 1912. Unclear; Honoring either Clemens Andreas Denhardt (1852–1928) or his brother, Gustav Denhardt (1856–1917), both German explorers and colonial functionaries.

dermatophaga: G. *dermatikos* (δερματικός), of skin, like skin + G. *phagos* (φάγος), glutton. *Microcaecilia dermatophaga* Wilkinson, Sherratt, Starace & Gower, 2013. [...from the Greek *derma*=skin and *phagos*=eating...].

Dermophis: G. *dermos* (δερμος), skin (in the sense of leather) + G. *ophis* (όφίς), snake, serpent. *Dermophis* Peters, 1880. [...Die Zusammensetzung *Dermophis*, ebenso wie *Dermochelys* (und nicht *Dermatochelys*) ist gebildet, wie das Aristotelische *dermopter-us*...]. Same root in *Dermophiidae* Taylor, 1969, *Dermophiinae* Taylor, 1969, *Dermophiina* — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021, *Dermophiinoa* — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021.

Diatriata: G. *dia-* (διά), through, across, by, over + L. *atrium*, a room which contains the hearth, fore-court, hall, principal room + L. *-ata*, pertaining to. Diatriata Wilkinson & Nussbaum, 2006. [“...We propose Diatriata, as a suitable rankless name for this suprafamilial clade comprising those caecilians with partial external division of their atrium...”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

diminutiva: L. *diminutivum*, form of the diminutive; diminutive. *Grandisonia diminutiva* Taylor, 1968. [“...smallest transformed specimen known, 64 mm). In the synonymy of *Dermophis sechellensis* Boulenger, 1911.

disossea: L. *dis-*, intensive prefix + L. *ossea*, bone-, made, consisting of bone; bone-like. *Caecilia disossea* Taylor, 1968. [“...I regard it essential that these forms with the eye covered solidly with bone be separated from those having an open socket...”].

dorsalis: L. *dorsalis*, pertaining to the back. *Caecilia dorsalis* Peters, 1877. [“...Auf dem Hinterrücken beginnt eine niedrige Längswulst, welche sich in das zusammengedrückte Schwanzrudiment fortsetzt, welches die Afteröffnung

um 2 Mm. überragt...”]. In the synonymy of *Potamotyphlus kaupii* (Berthold, 1859).

dubium: L. *dubium*, unclear, dubious, uncertain; variable. *Brasilotyphlus dubium* Correia, Nunes, Gamble, Maciel, Marques-Souza, Fouquet, Rodrigues & Mott, 2018. [“...The epithet *dubium* means “dubious”, reflecting our doubt whether or not *Brasilotyphlus* should be considered a synonym of *Microcaecilia*...”].

dulitensis: ? [Mount] Dulit, Sarawak, Borneo + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis dulitensis* Taylor, 1960. [“...(Mt.) Dulit + *ensis* (Latin) = place, locality, country...”].

dunni: Dunn + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names & nouns. *Caecilia dunni* Hershkovitz, 1938. Honoring Emmett Reid Dunn (1894–1956), US American herpetologist.

eburatus: L. *eburatus*, adorned with ivory; inlaid with ivory. *Dermophis eburatus* Taylor, 1968. [“...Color: Above, grayish-olive or brownish ivory...”]. In the synonymy of *Dermophis mexicanus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

eiselti: Eiselt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Typhlonectes eiselti* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Josef Eiselt (1912–2001), Austrian herpetologist. Today *Atretochoana eiselti* (Taylor, 1968).

elongata, elongatus: L. *elongata*, *-us*, prolonged, protracted. (1) *Caecilia elongata* Dunn, 1942. [...500 – 620 mm...]. Today *Oscacaecilia elongata* (Dunn, 1942). (2) *Ichthyophis elongatus* Taylor, 1965. [...body width in length 37 to 40 times...].

Eocaecilia: G. *eos* (ἑως), from *ios* (ἠώς), dawn or sunrise + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Eocaecilia* Jenkins & Walsh, 1993. [...Greek *Eo*, dawn: the dawn caecilian...].

ephele: L. *ephelis*, freckled. *Schistometopum ephele* Taylor, 1965. [...From Latin *ephelis* = freckled...]. In the synonymy of *Schistometopum thomense* (Bocage, 1873).

Epicrionops: G. *ep-icrion* (ἐπ-ἰκρίον), yard-arm (supporting a sail) + G. *ops* (ὄψ), eye. *Epicrionops* Boulenger, 1883. [...Tentacle minute, flap-shaped, close to

the anterior border of the eye..."]. Same root in *Epicriidei* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986.

epicrionopsoides: L. *Epicrionops*, a rhinatrematid genus due to Boulenger, 1883 (see this name) + L. *-oides*, or G. *-ειδός*, suffix indicating likeness. *Caecilia epicrionopsoides* Fernández-Roldán, Lynch & Medina-Rangel, 2023. [...The specific epithet is Greek (*epicrionops-oides*) and is given in reference to the peculiar condition of this *Caecilia* having two sets of secondary grooves, an anterior one found shortly behind the collars and a posterior one near the terminus. The name alludes the annulation pattern of rhinatrematid caecilians of the genus *Epicrionops*, which have very high groove counts along the body. Additionally, the new species seems very closely associated with streams, which is also similar to species of *Epicrionops*...]

Epicrium: G. *ep-icrion* (ἐπ-ἰκρίον), yard-arm (supporting a sail). *Epicrium* Wagler, 1828. [...truncus elongatus, aequalis, cylindraceo-depressiusculus...]. In the synonymy of *Ichthyophis* Fitzinger, 1826. Same root in *Epicria* Fitzinger, 1843, *Epicrina* Bonaparte, 1845, *Epicriidae* — Dubois, 1984, *Epicriilae* — Lescure,

Renous & Gasc, 1986, Epicriinae — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Epicrioidae — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Epicrioidae — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Epicrioides — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Epicriumidae — Anonymous, 1993.

equatorialis: *L. equatorialis*, related to Ecuador. *Osaecilia equatorialis* Taylor, 1973. [...from Dyott Farm, Km 121 from Quito, 6 km E Santo Domingo de los Colorados, Pichincha, Ecuador...].

erugatum: *L. erugatum*, with wrinkles or creases removed. *Chthonerpeton erugatum* Taylor, 1968. [...Conspicuous skin glands of two sorts, the larger ones often somewhat elevated and causing the surface to appear slightly granular...]. In the synonymy of *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

exile: *L. exile*, small, thin; poor. *Chthonerpeton exile* Nussbaum & Wilkinson, 1987. [...The name *exile* (Latin, *exilis*) refers to the relatively slender, delicate shape of the body and head...].

fasciata: *L. fasciata*, having band, strip; ribbon. *Nectocaecilia fasciata* Taylor, 1968. [?]. In the synon-

ymy of *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

fischeri: Fischer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Boulengerula fischeri* Nussbaum & Hinkel, 1994. Honoring Eberhard Fischer (1961–), German botanist.

flaviventer: *L. flavus*, yellow, golden, gold colored + *ventris*, stomach, womb; belly. *Dermophis flaviventer* Ahl, 1926. [...Oberseite gelblichbraun, Unterseite hell gelblichbraun...]. In the synonymy of *Dermophis sechellensis* Boulenger, 1911.

flavopunctata: *L. flavus*, yellow, golden, gold colored + *L. punctata*, punctuated; pointed. *Caecilia flavopunctata* Roze & Solano, 1963. [...Lateralmente, aparecen dos manchas amarillas por cada segmento, dando la impresión de ser dos líneas laterales que se extienden desde la porción posterior de la cabeza hasta el ano...].

forcarti: Forcart + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis forcarti* Taylor, 1965. Honoring Lothar Hendrich Emil Wilhelm Forcart-Müller (1902–1990),

Swiss herpetologist. In the synonymy of *Caecilia glutinosa* Linnaeus, 1758.

fredi: Fred + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Luetkenotyphlus fredi* Maciel, Castro, Sturaro, Silva, Ferreira, Santos, Risse-Quaioto, Barbosa, Oliveira, Sampaio & Schneider, 2019. Honoring Carlos Frederico (Fred) Duarte Rocha (1958–), Brazilian herpetologist.

fulleri: Fuller + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Herpele fulleri* Alcock, 1904. Honoring Sir Joseph Bampfylde Fuller (1854–1935), English colonial administrator in India. Today *Chikila fulleri* (Alcock, 1904).

gaiduwani: Gaiduwan + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Chikila gaiduwani* Kamei, Gower, Wilkinson & Biju, 2013. Honoring Gaiduwan Gaipuizei Kammei, from Kohima, Nagaland), first author's father.

gansi: Gans + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Uraeotyphlus gansi* Gower, Rajendran, Nussbaum & Wilkinson, 2008. Honoring Carl

Gans (1923–2009), US American herpetologist born in Germany.

garoensis: Ga. Garo [Hills], part of the Garo-Khasi range, Meghalaya, India (named after the Garo, native people inhabiting the area) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis garoensis* Pillai & Ravichandran, 1999. [“...Distribution: Garo Hills, Meghalaya...”].

garzonheydti: Garzon Heydt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Schistometopum garzonheydti* Taylor & Salvador, 1978. Honoring Jesús Garzon Heydt (1946–2023), Spanish naturalist. In the synonymy of *Geotrypetes seraphini* (Duméril, 1859).

Gegeneophis: *G. gegenes* (γηγενής), earthborn + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Gegeneophis* Peters, 1880. [“...Der von Hrn. Günther vorgeschlagene Name war schon 1816 von Hübner an eine Lepidopteren-gattung vergeben...”].

Gegenes: *G. gegenes* (γηγενής), earthborn. *Gegenes* Günther, 1876 “1875”. Preoccupied by *Gegenes* Hübner, 1816 (Lepidoptera). In the synonymy of *Gegeneophis* Peters, 1880.

Georynchii: G. *geo-* (γεω-), land, earth + G. *rhynchos* (ῥύγχος), snout. *Georynchii* Wagler, 1828. [...Wühler, Irdler, Grabler ...]. Wagler (1828) used ‘Georychi’. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

Geotrypetes: G. *geo-* (γεω-), land, earth + G. *trypetes* (τρυπητής), borer. *Geotrypetes* Peters, 1880. [...γέα, τρυπητής...]. Same root in *Geotrypetoidea* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Geotrypetinoidea* – Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021.

gilbertogili: Gilberto Gil + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Rhinatrema gilbertogili* Maciel, Sampaio, Hoogmoed & Schneider, 2018. Honoring Gilberto Passos Gil Moreira (1942–), Brazilian music, composer, and singer.

glandulosus: L. *glandula*, gland (literally: a little acorn) + L. *-osus*, suffix denoting abundance. (1) *Dermophis glandulosus* Taylor, 1955. [...Latin, *glandulosus* = glandulose...]. (2) *Ichthyophis glandulosus* Taylor, 1923. [...on each side of body is a broad dorso-lateral glandular fold which extends from head along body to a point a short distance in front of tail; this fold is strongly defined, of equal prominence its entire length...].

glutinosa: L. *glutinosus*, viscous, sticky, glutinous. *Caecilia glutinosa* Linnaeus, 1758. [?]. Today *Ichthyophis glutinosus* (Linnaeus, 1758).

goaensis: P. Goa (in turn, from K. गोंय, patch of tall grass, referring to the lush greenery or abundant vegetation that characterized the area), state on the southwestern coast of India + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Gegeneophis goaensis* Bhatta, Dinesh, Prashanth & Kulkarni, 2007. [...The species is named after Goa where the type locality is situated...].

goweri: Gower + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia goweri* Fernández-Roldán & Lynch, 2021. Honoring David J. Gower (1969–), British herpetologist.

gracilior: L. *gracilis*, slender, thin, slim, slight; fine, narrow + L. *-ior*, comparative suffix. *Dermophis gracilior* Günther, 1902. [...Habit moderate, the circumference of the body being nearly one-sixth of its length...].

gracilis: L. *gracilis*, slender, thin, slim, slight; fine. *Caecilia gracilis* Shaw, 1802. [...Slender *Caecilia*...].

grandis: L. *grandis*, full-grown, grown up; large, great, grand, tall, lofty; powerful. *Microcaecilia grandis* Wilkinson, Nussbaum & Hoogmoed, 2010. [“...The species is named for its large size...”].

grandisonae: Grandison + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. *Geotrypetes grandisonae* Taylor, 1970. Honoring Alice Georgie Cruickshank Grandison (1927–2014), British herpetologist. Today *Sylvacaecilia grandisonae* (Taylor, 1970).

Grandisonia: Grandison + L. *-ia*, dedicative suffix. *Grandisonia* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Alice Georgie Cruickshank Grandison (1927–2014), British herpetologist. Same root in *Grandisoniidae* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Grandisoniilae* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Grandisoniina* — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021, *Grandisoniinia* — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021.

gregorii: Gregory + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Dermophis gregorii* Boulenger, 1895 “1894”. Honoring John Walter Gregory (1864–1932), British geologist and explorer. Today *Schistometopum gregorii* (Boulenger, 1895).

guarantanus: P. Guarantã do Norte, Mato Grosso, Brazil; from T. *guara-antã*, hard wood (vernacular name of diverse species of hardwood trees, including *Cupania uraguensis* and *Esenbeckia leiocarpa*) + L. *-anus*, belonging to. *Brasilotyphlus guarantanus* Maciel, Mott & Hoogmoed, 2009. [“...The name of the species refers to the type-locality...”].

guentheri, guntheri: Günther + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. (1) *Caecilia guntheri* Dunn, 1942. (2) *Hypogeophis guentheri* Boulenger, 1882. Honoring Albert Carl Ludwig Gotthilf Günther (1830–1914), German-born British zoologist. In the synonymy of *Hypogeophis rostratus* (Cuvier, 1829).

Gymnophiona: G. *gymnos* (γυμνός), naked + G. *ophis* (όφις), snake, serpent. *Gymnophiona* Rafinesque, 1815. [“...*I ginoffi. Corpo senza squame...*”]. Same root in *Gymnophia* Rafinesque, 1814, *Gymnodermia* Rafinesque, 1815, *Gymnophides* Latreille, 1825, *Gymnophidia* Müller, 1831.

Gymnophis: G. *gymnos* (γυμνός), naked + G. *ophis* (όφις), snake, serpent. *Gymnophis* — Barbour, 1924. [?]. Incorrect subsequent spelling of *Gymnopsis* Peters, 1874.

Gymnopsis: *G. gymnos* (γυμνός), naked + *G. ops* (ὄψ), eye. (1) *Gymnopsis* Peters, 1874. [...γυμνός, ὄψ...]. (2) Same root in *Gymnopiilae* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986.

hardyi: Hardy + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Siphonops hardyi* Boulenger, 1888. Honoring F. Hardy du Dréneuf, Belgian collector and traveler, active in Brazil at the end of the XIX century.

hasselti: Hasselt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Epicrium hasselti* Wagler, 1828; in the synonymy of *Ichthyophis hypocyaneus* (Van Hasselt in Boie, 1827). (2) *Ichthyophis hasselti* Fitzinger, 1826, *nomen nudum*; in the synonymy of *Ichthyophis hypocyaneus* (Van Hasselt in Boie, 1827). Honoring Johan Coenraad van Hasselt (1797–1823), Dutch biologist.

haydee: S. *Haydée*, feminine name, Spanish and French form of Haidee. Perhaps intended to derive from Greek αἰδοῖος meaning modest, reverent. This name was created by Lord Byron for a character (written as Haidée) in his 1819 poem *Don Juan*. *Chthonerpeton haydee* Roze, 1963. Hon-

oring Haydée Solano de Chacin (1922–1993), Venezuelan herpetologist. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes natans* (Fischer, 1880).

Hedraeoglossi: *G. hedraios* (ἔδραϊος), sitting, sedentary + *G. glossa* (γλῶσσα), tongue. *Hedraeoglossi* Wagler, 1828. [...Haftzüngler ...]. In the synonymy of *Caeciliidae* Rafinesque, 1814.

hellmichi: Hellmich + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Chthonerpeton hellmichi* Taylor, 1968. Probably Honoring Karl George Walter Hellmich (1906–1974), German herpetologist. In the synonymy of *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

Herpele: *G. herpele* (ἔρπήλη), a kind of worm. *Herpele* Peters, 1880. [...ἔρπήλη...]. Same root in *Herpelidae* Laurent, 1984, *Herpelinae* Laurent, 1984, *Herpeloidi* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Herpeliini* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Herpeliti* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986.

humphreyi: Humphrey + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis humphreyi* Taylor, 1973.

Honoring Philip Humphrey (1926–2009), US American ornithologist.

husaini: Husain + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis husaini* Pillai & Ravichandran, 1999. Honoring Akhlaq Husain, Zoological Survey of India, Dehra Dun, who collected the specimen and provided valuable data. In the synonymy of *Ichthyophis garoensis* Pillai & Ravichandran, 1999.

hypereumeces: G. *hyper* (ὑπέρ), beyond, over, above, very + G. *eumêkes* (εὐ-μήκης), very long, extensive, impressive. *Osaecilia hypereumeces* Taylor, 1968. [“...A slender, much-elongated species, reaching a known length of 640 mm...”].

hypocyanea: G. *hypo* (ὑπό), beneath, below, under + G. *kyaneos* (κυάνεος), glossy black or dark blue. *Caecilia hypocyanea* Van Hasselt in Boie, 1827. [“...*Supra ex olivaceo obscura, subtus chalybea linea laterali flavo punctata...*”]. Today *Ichthyophis hypocyaneus* (Van Hasselt in Boie, 1827).

Hypogeophis: G. *hypogeios* (υπόγειος), underground + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Hy-*

pogeophis Peters, 1880. [?].

ibiara: T. *ibiara*, corr. *yby-ra*, what is born from the ground. *Caecilia ibiara* Daudin, 1803 “An. XI”. [“... Le nom qui sert à désigner cette espèce a été employé par Marcgrave, d’après les habitans du Brésil, pour l’amphisbène enfumé...”]. Substitute name for *Caecilia tentaculata*. In the synonymy of *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758.

Ichthyophis: G. *ichthys* (ἰχθύς), fish + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Ichthyophis* Fitzinger, 1826. [“... Linne’s *Caecilia glutinosa* und eine neue Art aus Java, haben einen deutlich plattgedrückten Körper mit zugespitztem Ende, welcher den übrigen Coecilen durchaus fehlt, und hieraufist der generische Unterschied gegründet...”]. Same root in *Ichthyophiidae* Taylor, 1968, *Ichthyophidinae* — Wollenberg & Measey, 2009, *Ichthyophioidea* — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021.

Idiocranium: G. *idios* (ἴδιος), peculiar, separate, distinct + G. *cranium* (κρᾶνιον), skull. *Idiocranium* Parker, 1936. [“...This new genus is distinguished from any caecilian hitherto described by the great reduction of the frontal bones, which do not meet the maxillaries but permit the naso-premaxillaries to

form a suture with the squamosals...”].

inca: Q. [*Sapa*] *Inka*, the only Inca, was the Emperor of the Andean, pre-Columbian Inca Empire (Tawantinsuyu). *Caecilia inca* Taylor, 1973. [“...The name “*inca*” refers to the rulers of the primitive inhabitants of Perú...”].

indistinctus: L. *indistinctum*, not separated; indistinct, obscure. *Siphonops indistinctus* Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862 “1861”. [“...*annuli corporis indistincti & incompleti...*”]. Today *Chthonerpeton indistinctum* (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862).

Indotyphlus: L. *indo*, Indian, inhabitant of India + G. *typhlos* (τυφλος), blind (frequent ending in caecilian names). *Indotyphlus* Taylor, 1960. [“...From *Indo*, referring to India, + *typhlos* Gr. = blind...”]. Same root in *Indotyphlina* Lescure, Renault & Gasc, 1986, *Indotyphlidae* — Wilkinson, San Mauro, Sherratt & Gower, 2011, *Indotyphlina* — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021.

insulanus: L. *insula*, island + L. *-anus*, belonging to. *Siphonops insulanus* Ihering, 1911. [“...Est. S. Paulo, Ilha Victoria e Ilha de São Sebastião...”]. Today *Luetkenotyphlus insulanus* (Ihering, 1911).

intermedia: L. *intermedia*, intermediate. *Caecilia intermedia* Boulenger, 1913. [“...Intermediate between *C. tentaculata* L. and *C. pachynema* Gthr...”]. Either synonym of *Caecilia dunni* Hershkovitz, 1938 or *Caecilia nigricans* Boulenger, 1902, *vide* Frost 2023.

Interrupta, interruptus: L. *interrupta*, *-us*, drive a gap in, break up; cut short, interrupt. (1) *Caecilia interrupta* Cuvier, 1829. [“...*Caec. interrupta*, Nob. , où les lignes blanches des anneaux ne se correspondent pas en dessous...”]. In the synonymy of *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1820). (2) *Uraeotyphlus interruptus* Pillai & Ravichandran, 1999. [“...The more important characters for the erection of a new taxon are the interrupted nature of the body folds...”].

isthmica: L. *isthmica*, pertaining, belonging to the isthmus. *Caecilia isthmica* Cope, 1877. [“...This species was included in the collection made by Commander Selfridge on the East side of the Isthmus of Darien...”].

iwokramae: Mk. Iwokrama [Forest], natural reserve in central Guyana (in turn, from Mk. Iwokrama, place of refuge). *Caecilita iwokramae* Wake & Donnelly, 2010. [“...The species is named for the forest

in which the type specimen was discovered...”]. Today *Microcaecilia iwokramae* (Wake & Donnelly, 2010).

iyob: E. *iyob*, acronym for International Year of Biodiversity. *Microcaecilia iyob* Wilkinson & Kok, 2010. [“...The species is named to commemorate the International Year of Biodiversity (2010) to serve as a reminder that much biodiversity is undescribed and much sampled biodiversity is poorly understood taxonomically...”]

javanicus: L. *javanicus*, belonging to Java, one of the Indonesian Sunda Islands [in turn, from Sa. Sawa (यव), barley]. *Ichthyophis javanicus* Taylor, 1960. [“...Java + *icus* = belonging to, pertaining to...”].

kaupii: Kaupp + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia kaupii* Berthold, 1859. Honoring Johann Jakob von Kaup (1803–1873), German zoologist. Today *Potamotyphlus kaupii* (Berthold, 1859).

khumhzi: ? Khumhzi village, Tamenglong district, Manipur, India. *Ichthyophis khumhzi* Kamei, Wilkinson, Gower & Biju, 2009. [“...Named after Khumhzi village, where the type series was collected...”].

kirkii: Kirk + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Scolecormorphus kirkii* Boulenger, 1883. Honoring Sir John Kirk (1832–1922), British diplomat, explorer and naturalist.

kodaguensis: ? Kodagu, district on the eastern slopes of the Western Ghats, Karnataka state, India. *Ichthyophis kodaguensis* Wilkinson, Gower, Govindappa & Venkatachalaiah, 2007. [“...The specific epithet reflects the provenance of the type specimens from the District of Kodagu (also known as Coorg) in Southern Karnataka, India...”].

koepckeorum: Koepcke + L. *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. *Osaecilia koepckeorum* Wake, 1984. Honoring Hans-Wilhelm Koepcke (1914–2000) and his wife Maria (née Maria Emilia Ana von Mikulicz-Radecki, 1924–1971), German ornithologists.

kohtaoensis: Th. Koh Tao Island, part of the Chumphon Archipelago in the Gulf of Thailand; in turn, from Thai เกาะเต่า, turtle island. *Ichthyophis kohtaoensis* Taylor, 1960. [“...The species is named from the island + *ensis* (Latin) place, country...”].

krishni: Krishna + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honoring Krishna Farms, a dairy farm in Karnataka, India. *Gegeneophis krishni* Pillai & Ravichandran, 1999. [... Krishna Farms, Gurpur, Karnataka...].

ladigesi: Ladiges + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Nectocaecilia ladigesi* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Werner Ladiges (1910–1984), German ichthyologist. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

lakimi: Lakim + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis lakimi* Nishikawa, Matsui & Yambun, 2012. Honoring Maklarin B. Lakim (?), then in charge of the research division of Sabah Parks, Kota Kinabalu, Malaysia.

lamottei: Lamotte + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Scolecormorphus lamottei* Nussbaum, 1981. Honoring Maxime Lamotte (1920-2007), French biologist and geneticist. Today *Crotaphatrema lamottei* (Nussbaum, 1981).

laosensis: La. Laos, landlocked country in SE Asia; from Lao people, a Tai ethnic group native to Southeast Asia + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis laosensis* Taylor, 1969. [...Specimen from “Haut Laos.”...].

larutensis: Ma. Larut [Hills], Perak, Malaysia (from Ma. *larut*, soluble or dissolve) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis larutensis* Taylor, 1960. [...Larut (Mts.) + ensis (Latin) = place, locality, country...].

larvatus: L. *larva*, ghost-like, masked, (used for the distinct juvenile form of many animals before metamorphosing into their next stage) + L. *-atus*, suffix indicating condition of. *Dermophis larvatus* Ahl, 1934. Today *Grandisonia larvata* (Ahl, 1934).

lativittatus: L. *latus*, wide, broad + L. *vittatus*, wearing or carrying a ritual band or ribbon. *Epicrionops lativittatus* Taylor, 1968. [...A short thick-bodied species with a very broad (5½-, 7mm) lateral yellow stripe on each side...].

lenticulata: L. *lenticulata*, provided with lenses. *Caecilia lenticulata* Tschudi, 1838. Error for *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758.

leucocephala: G. *leuco* (λευκος), white + G. *képhala* (κεφάλη), head. *Caecilia leucocephala* Taylor, 1968. [“...Head light grayish cream to old ivory...”].

leucoderus: G. *leuco* (λευκος), white + G. *deros* (δερως), skin, hide. *Siphonops leucoderus* Taylor, 1968. [“...Dark brown dorsally, lighter beneath; a white area on chin and throat...”].

lionneti: Lionnet + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Hypogeophis rostratus lionneti* Taylor, 1969. Honoring Mr. J. F. Guy Lionnet (1922–2007), Mauritian-Seychellois agronomist, naturalist, linguist, playwright and historian. In the synonymy of *Hypogeophis rostratus* (Cuvier, 1829).

longicephalus: L. *longus*, long + G. *képhala* (κεφάλη), head. *Ichthyophis longicephalus* Pillai, 1986. [“...Head comparatively longer...”].

Luetkenotyphlus: Lütken + G. *typhlos* (τυφλος), blind. *Luetkenotyphlus* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Christian (not Charles, as stated by Taylor) Frederik Lütken (1827–1901), Danish zoologist.

lumbricoïdaea: L. *lumbricus*, earthworm + L. *-oïdes*, or G. *-ειδός*, suffix indicating likeness. *Caecilia lumbricoïdaea* Daudin, 1803 “An. XI”. [“...On ne peut mieux comparer cette cécilie qu’à un lombric ou ver de terre, à cause de sa forme qui est mince, très-longue, d’égale grosseur depuis la tête jusqu’au bout de la queue...”]. In the synonymy of *Caecilia gracilis* Shaw, 1802.

macrodonta: G. *makros* (μακρός), long; large in size or degree, great + G. *odontia* (οδόντια), teeth. *Caecilia macrodonta* Fernández-Roldán, Lynch & Medina-Rangel, 2023. [“...The specific epithet is derived from the Greek words *macro* (large) and *odonto* (teeth), and roughly translates as ‘bigtooth’. We consider the name to be fitting one because of all the Colombian species of the genus *Caecilia*, this one possesses the largest and thickest dentary teeth, suggesting a specialized diet...”].

maculatus: L. *maculatus*, spotted. *Siphonops paulensis* var. *maculatus* Sawaya, 1937. [“...Do mesmo modo que em *S. annulatus*, aqui nesta especie deparei com dois exemplares ... providos de manchas esbranquiçadas absolutamente idênticas às já descritas para a variedade daquela especie...”]. In

the synonymy of *Siphonops paulensis* Boettger, 1892.

madhavai: Madhava + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gegeneophis madhavai* Bhatta & Srinivasa, 2004. Honoring Madhava Bhat, Madhavarao Bhide, Madhava Anantha Pai, and Madhava Gadgil “for supporting the first author’s research into caecilians”.

maharashtraensis: M. Maharashtra, an Indian state + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. It has been suggested that the name derives from a tribe or dynasty of chiefs ruling in the Deccan region, or from the Sanskrit, meaning great nation. *Indotyphlus maharashtraensis* Giri, Wilkinson & Gower, 2004. [“...The species is named for Maharashtra, the Indian State within which the type locality lies...”].

malabarensis: ? Malabar, probably from Tm. *Malai*, mountain and Tm. *Barum*, slope + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis malabarensis* Taylor, 1960. [“... Malabar + *ensis*, place locality of...”]. In the synonymy of *Uraeotyphlus bombayensis* (Taylor, 1960).

malabarica: ? Malabar, probably from Tm. *Malai*, mountain and Tm. *Barum*, slope+ L. *-ica*, suffix used to indicate possession or association with something. *Cecilia malabarica* Beddome, 1870. [“... Malabar - rare...”]. Today *Uraeotyphlus malabaricus* (Beddome, 1870).

marcusi: Marcus + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia marcusi* Wake, 1985. Honoring Harry Marcus, German physician working in Bolivia. In the synonymy of *Caecilia mertensi* Taylor, 1973

marmoratus: L. *marmoratus*, marbled; overlaid with marble. (1) *Epicrionops marmoratus* Taylor, 1968. [“...The ground color cream-white with spots, flecks, and dots of lavender pigment...”]. (2) *Siphonops annulatus* var. *marmoratus* Sawaya, 1937. [“...Dentre os exemplares de *S. annulatus* examinados, 32 apresentam grande numero de manchas formadas de um conjunto de semicírculos ou segmentos de arcos de parabolos, ou ainda de espiraes, concêntricos, localizados nos flancos, no dorso e no abdômen, sem uma distribuição uniforme ...Estes traços podem ainda mostrar-se emaranhados, cruzando-se entre si na superfície das pregas anulares em

diversas direcções, dando á pelle um aspecto rajado...”]. In the synonymy of *Siphonops annulatus* (Mikan, 1820).

marvaleewakeae: Marvalee Wake + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating the genitive of feminine names and nouns. *Microcaecilia marvaleewakeae* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2013. Honoring Marvalee Hendricks Wake (1939–), US American herpetologist.

melanochrus: *G. melanos* (μέλανος), black + *G. chros* (χρῶς), skin, flesh. *Potomotyphlus melanochrus* Taylor, 1968. [“...The color is deep black throughout...”]. In the synonymy of *Potomotyphlus kaupii* (Berthold, 1859).

menoni: Menon + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Uraeotyphlus menoni* Annandale, 1913. Honoring Konkoth Ramunni Menon (1872–1949), Indian zoologist.

mertensi: Mertens + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia mertensi* Taylor, 1973. Honoring Robert Friedrich Wilhelm Mertens (1894–1975), German herpetologist.

mexicanus: L. *mexicanus*, from México. *Siphonops mexicanus* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. [“...Ce Siphonops est originaire du Mexique...”]. Today *Dermophis mexicanus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

mhadeiensis: Sa. Mahadayi or Mhadei, river in the state of Goa, India (probably Honoring Mahadevi, महादेवी, the supreme goddess in the Shaktism sect of Hinduism) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Gegeneophis mhadeiensis* Bhatta, Dinesh, Prashanth & Kulkarni, 2007. [“...The species is named after the river Mhadei on the bank of one of the tributaries of which the type locality is situated...”].

Microcaecilia: *G. mikros* (μικρός), small + L. *Caecilia*, caecilian genus due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Microcaecilia* Taylor, 1968. [“...Small species with eye visible or invisible externally...”]. Same root in *Microcaeciliinoa* Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021.

microcephalum: *G. mikros* (μικρός), small + *képhala* (κεφάλη), head. *Chthonerpeton microcephalum* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937. [“...Cabeça pequena, egualando a 1/2 do maior diametro do corpo...”]. In the syn-

onymy of *Potamotyphlus kaupii* (Berthold, 1859).

***micropodia*:** G. *mikros* (μικρός), small + G. *podos* (ποδος), foot. *Eocaecilia micropodia* Jenkins & Walsh, 1993. [...*mikros*, small; *pous*, foot: in reference to the diminutive limbs...].

***Mimosiphonops*:** L. *mimus*, mime; farce; actor in mimes + L. *Siphonops*, genus of gymnophiones due to Wagler, 1828 (see this name). *Mimosiphonops* Taylor, 1968. [...A genus generally resembling *Siphonops annulatus*...].

***Minascaecilia*:** S. [Sierra de las] Minas, mountain range in the departments of Baja Verapaz, Alta Verapaz, El Progreso, Zacapa, and Izabal, Guatemala + L. *Caecilia*, genus of gymnophiona due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Minascaecilia* Wake & Campbell, 1983. [...The generic name reflects the general region inhabited by the taxon (Minas-, for the Sierra de las Minas of east-central Guatemala) and-caecilia, for the group of genera to which the taxon is most similar (the small and attenuate species included in *Caecilia*, and its relatives)...]. In the synonymy of *Gymnopsis* Peters, 1874.

***mindanaoensis*:** S. Mindanao (Spanish corruption of Ce. *maguindanao*, people of the lake or flood plains), the second-largest island in the Philippines archipelago + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis mindanaoensis* Taylor, 1960. [...Mindanao + *ensis* (Latin) = place, country of...].

***monbaroni*:** Monbaron + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. Honoring Michel Monbaron (1942-), Swiss geologist.

***monochrous*:** G. *monos* (μόνος), alone (without the presence of others) + G. *chrous* (χρως) color; the color of the skin; complexion. *Epicrium monochrous* Bleeker, 1858. [...Het is van eene violetbruine kleur over het geheele ligchaam en slechts iets lichter gekleurd aan de ondervlakte van den kop...]. Today *Ichthyophis monochrous* (Bleeker, 1858).

***montanus*:** L. *montanus*, from the mountains; mountain dweller. *Hypogeophis montanus* Maddock, Wilkinson & Gower, 2018. [...The specific epithet is in reference to the restricted, high elevation distribution of the species, known only from above 700 m, on the highest mountains in the Seychelles...].

moustakius: *G. mústakos* (μύστακος), moustache. *Ichthyophis moustakius* Kamei, Wilkinson, Gower & Biju, 2009. [...The species name is derived from the Greek word *moustakius*, meaning moustache, referring to the distinctive yellow, arched stripes extending between the TAs and nares...].

multicolor: *L. multicolor*, many-colored. *Ichthyophis multicolor* Wilkinson, Presswell, Sherratt, Papadopoulou & Gower, 2014. [...Named for its having more distinct colours than most other *Ichthyophis*...].

multiplicata, multiplicatus: *L. multiplicata*, -us, multiply; repeat; increase (number, quantity, extent). (1) *Cryptopsophis multiplicatus* Boulenger, 1883. [?]. In the synonymy of *Gymnopsis multiplicata* Peters, 1874. (2) *Gymnopsis multiplicata* Peters, 1874. [...Zähne kegelförmig, ziemlich kurz und zahlreich (im Oberkieferende etwa 18 an jeder Seite)...]. (3) *Herpele multiplicata* Nieden, 1912. [...Die Zahl der Hautfalten ist merklich größer als bei *Herpele squalostoma*...].

museugoeldi: *P. Museu Goeldi. Caecilia museugoeldi* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2018. Honoring the Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi, Belém,

Pará, Brazil, the oldest research institution in the Amazon region.

nadkarnii: *Nadkarni L. -ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gegeneophis nadkarnii* Bhatta & Prashanth, 2004. Honoring Vinayaka Baburao Nadkarni (1933-2020), Indian zoologist.

narayani: *Narayan + L. -i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Uraeotyphlus narayani* Seshachar, 1939. Honoring C. R. Narayan Rao (1882-1960), Indian herpetologist.

natans: *L. natans*, swimming. *Caecilia natans* Fischer In Peters, 1880 "1879". [...Aus dem Cauca, Nebenfluss mit festem Kiesgrund des Magdalenenflusses, Neu Granada...]. Today *Typhlonectes natans* (Fischer, 1880)

Nectocaecilia: *G. nektes* (νηκτης), swimmer + *L. Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Nectocaecilia* Taylor, 1968. [...two large narial plugs on tongue...].

Neocaecilia: *G. neos* (νεός) + new, young, recent + *L. Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Neocaecilia*

Wilkinson & Nussbaum, 2006. [...For this reason, we prefer the anatomically neutral *Neocaecilia* as a rankless epithet for the suprafamilial clade including all caecilians with jaw-closing muscles that do not extend onto the top of the skull from the adductor chamber..."]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

nguyenorum: Nguyen + L. *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. *Ichthyophis nguyenorum* Nishikawa, Matsui & Orlov, 2012. Honoring the brothers Nguyen Quang Truong (1975–) and Nguyen Thien Tao (1982–), Vietnamese herpetologists.

nicefori: Nicéforo + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gymnophis nicefori* Barbour, 1924. Honoring Brother Nicéforo María, né Antoine Rouhaire Siazade (1888–1980), French priest and naturalist active in Colombia. Today *Microcaecilia nicefori* (Barbour, 1924).

niedeni: Nieden + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Boulengerula niedeni* Müller, Measey, Loader & Malonza, 2005. Honoring Fritz Nieden (1883–1942), German zoologist.

nigricans: L. *nigricans*, to be blackish. *Caecilia nigricans* Boulenger, 1902. [...Blackish; lips yellowish...].

nigroflavus: L. *nigrum*, black, dark + L. *flavus*, yellow, golden, gold colored. *Ichthyophis nigroflavus* Taylor, 1960. [...*nigro* (Latin) = black + *flavus* (Latin) = yellow...].

nigrum: L. *nigrum*, black, dark. *Rhinatrema nigrum* Dunn, 1942. [...Uniformly dark...].

noblei: Noble + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Epicrionops petersi noblei* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Gladwyn Kingsley Noble (1894–1940), US American herpetologist. In the synonymy of *Epicrionops petersi* Taylor, 1968.

noctinectes: L. *noctis*, night + G. *nektēs* (νηκτης), swimmer. *Chthonerpeton noctinectes* da Silva, Britto-Pereira & Caramaschi, 2003. {...The specific name is an adjective derived from *nocti* (Latin [*nox, noctis*] nocturnal) and *nectēs* (Greek [*nektion, nektos*] swimmer), as an allusion to the nocturnal swimming activity of the species....}.

nokrekensis: ? Nokrek, a Biosphere Reserve in Sasatgre, Meghalaya, West Garo Hills, India. [...The species name reflects the name of the Biosphere Reserve from where *Ichthyophis nokrekensis* Mathew & Sen, 2009. the type materials were collected...].

Nuda: L. *nudus*, naked, bare, unclothed, stripped, uncovered, exposed. Nuda Fitzinger, 1826. [...*Nuden...*]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

oaxacae: S. Oaxaca, Mexican city and state, from Náhuatl (Na). *Huaxyacac*, on the top of the huaje (a tree of the genus *Leucaena*) + L. -ae, suffix indicating pertenance. *Gymnopsis multiplicata oaxacae* Mertens, 1930 "1929". [...Terra typica: Cafetal Concordia, 600 m. Höhe (zwischen Puerto Angel und Salina Cruz), Staat Oaxaca, Mexiko...]. Today *Dermophis oaxacae* (Mertens, 1930).

obesus: L. *obesus*, fat, stout, plump. *Typhlonectes obesus* Taylor, 1968. [...A cylindrical, thick-bodied species...]. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes compressicauda* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

occidentalis: L. *occidentalis*, of, pertaining to, connected with, com-

ing from the west. (1) *Caecilia occidentalis* Taylor, 1968. [...From near Popayan, Cauca, Colombia...]. (2) *Dermophis occidentalis* Taylor, 1955. [...Latin, *occidentalis* = western...]. (3) *Geotrypetes seraphini occidentalis* Parker, 1936. [...The western subspecies of *seraphini* may be known by the above name...]. In the synonymy of *Geotrypetes seraphini* (Duméril, 1859).

ochrocephala: G. *ochra* (ὄχρα), ochre, pale yellow + G. *céphala* (κεφαλή), head. *Coecilia ochrocephala* Cope, 1866. [...Head lighter, clouded yellowish-olive ...lower lip and jaw yellowish...]. Today *Oscacilia ochrocephala* (Cope, 1866).

oligozonus: G. *oligos* (ὀλίγος), little in size or weight; insignificant + L. *zona*, belt, girdle, zone. *Siphonops oligozonus* Cope, 1877. [...The annuli continue to the vent, and those of the secondary series commence much posterior to the point of beginning in the other species...]. In the synonymy of *Gymnopsis syntrema* (Cope, 1866).

onorei: Onore + L. -i, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names

and nouns. *Chthonerpeton onorei* Nussbaum, 1986. Honoring Father Giovanni Onore (1941–), Italian Marianist missionary priest and zoologist, active in Ecuador.

oommeni: Oommen + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Uraeotyphlus oommeni* Gower & Wilkinson, 2007. Honoring Oommen V. Oommen (1949–), Indian herpetologist.

Ophiomorpha: G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent + G. *morpha* (μορφή), form, shape, appearance. *Ophiomorpha* Van der Hoeven, 1855. [“...*Corpus anguiforme, teres...*”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

Ophiosomes: G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent + G. *soma* (σῶμα), body of man or beast. *Ophiosomes* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. [“...Parmi les Batraciens, un groupe entier a été long-temps rangé dans l’ordre des Ophidiens, c’est celui des Ophiosomes ou Péromèles...”]. Same root in *Ophiosoma* Lichtenstein & Martens, 1856 In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

orientalis: L. *orientalis*, coming from the east. (1) *Caecilia orientalis* Taylor, 1968. [“...La Bonita, Napo-Pastaza Prov., Ecuador...”]. (2)

Gegeneophis orientalis Agarwal, Wilkinson, Mohapatra, Dutta, Giri & Gower, 2013. [“...The specific epithet is an adjective derived from the Latin *oriens* for “East” in reference to this being the first *Gegeneophis* from the Eastern Ghats...”].

orthoplicatus: G. *orthos* (ὀρθος), straight, steep; upright, standing + L. *plicatus*, folded. *Ichthyophis orthoplicatus* Taylor, 1965. [“...Grooves and folds not angulate on venter...”].

osae: S. [Península de] Osa, Costa Rica (in turn, named after a local cacique or tribal chief named Osa, first contacted by the Spanish explorer Gil González Dávila around 1522) + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating pertinence. *Osaecilia osae* Lahanas & Savage, 1992. [“...adult female collected from the airstrip at La Sirena, Peninsula de Osa, Canton de Osa, Puntarenas Province, Costa Rica...”].

Osaecilia: L. *os*, bone, + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus (1758); in turn, from L. *caecus*, blind. *Osaecilia* Taylor, 1968. [“...Eye buried under bone & may or may not be visible through the bone...”]. Same root in *Osaecilioidae* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986.

oxyura: G. *oxys* (οξύς), sharp, acute + G. *oura* (οὐρά), tail. *Caecilia oxyura* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. [“...extrémité du tronc cylindrique; queue pointue...”]. Today *Uraeotyphlus oxyurus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

pachynema: G. *pachy* (παχύς), thick + G. *nema* (νήμα), thread. *Caecilia pachynema* Günther, 1859. [“...The length of the body is to its greatest diameter as 92:1...”].

palmeri: Palmer + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia palmeri* Boulenger, 1913. Honoring Mervyn George Palmer (1882–1954), English naturalist, traveler and collector in Central and South America. In the synonymy of *Caecilia nigricans* Boulenger, 1902.

pareshi: Paresh + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gegeneophis pareshi* Giri, Gower, Gaikwad & Wilkinson, 2011. Honoring Paresh Porob, Indian range forest officer in Goa, “...in recognition of his dedicated efforts to conserve and promote a love and understanding of wildlife and the natural environment, especially in Goa...”.

parkeri: Parker + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Rhinatrema parkeri* Dunn, 1942. Honoring Hampton Wildman Parker (1897–1968), British herpetologist. Today *Epicrionops parkeri* (Dunn, 1942).

Parvicaecilia: L. *parvus*, small, little; unimportant + L. *Caecilia*, caecilian genus due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Parvicaecilia* Taylor, 1968. [“...Slender, diminutive species...”].

parviceps: L. *parvus*, small + L. *-ceps*, from L. *caput*, head. *Siphonops parviceps* Dunn, 1924 [“...A *Siphonops* with head much smaller than body in diameter...”]. Today *Dermophis parviceps* (Dunn, 1924).

paucidentulus: L. *paucus*, little, small in quantity or extent + L. *dentulus*, from L. *dentatus*, toothed, having teeth. *Ichthyophis paucidentulus* Taylor, 1960. [“...The name *paucidentulus* is derived from Latin *paucus*, few; *dentatis*, toothed, in reference to the fact that there are only three instead of four sets of teeth...”].

paucisulcus: L. *paucus*, little, small in quantity or extent + L. *sulcus*,

furrow. *Ichthyophis paucisulcus* Taylor, 1960. [...*pauci* (Latin) = few + *sulcus* (Latin) = groove...].

paulensis: P. [São] Paulo, Brazilian city and state + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Siphonops paulensis* Boettger, 1892. [...Erw. São Paulo, Brasilien ...].

pauli: Paul + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis pauli* Nishikawa, Matsui, Sudin & Wong, 2013. Honoring Paul Yambun, Malay zoologist, one of the collectors of this species.

peninsularis: L. *peninsularis*, from the peninsula. *Ichthyophis peninsularis* Taylor, 1960. [...*Peninsula* (Latin) referring to peninsular India...]. In the synonymy of *Uraeotyphlus bombayensis* (Taylor, 1960).

perdita: L. *perditus*, ruined; broken, debilitated. *Caecilia perdita* Taylor, 1968. [?].

perissodus: G. *perissos* (περισσός), beyond what is normal in number or size + G. *odoús* (οδοῦς), tooth (human or animal) *Chthonerpeton perissodus* Nussbaum & Wilkinson 1987. [...This species has more premaxillary-maxillary teeth than any other *Chthonerpe-*

ton, hence the name *perissodus*, from *perissos* (Greek, more than the usual number of) and *odous* (Greek, tooth)...].

Péromèles: G. *peros* (πηρός), disabled in a limb, maimed + G. *melos* (μέλος), limb. *Péromèles* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. [?]. Same root in *Peromela* Bonaparte, 1850, *Concept. Syst. Herpetol. Amph.*: 1. Subclass to contain caecilians (*Batrachophidii*) & *Batrachosaurus* (*Batrachosaurii*). In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

peruvianum: L. *peruvianum*, from Perú, a South American country. *Rhinatrema peruvianum* Boulenger, 1902. [...*Marcapata Valley*, E. Peru...]. Today *Epicrionops peruvianus* (Boulenger, 1902)

petersi: Peters + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Epicrionops petersi petersi* Taylor, 1968. Honoring James Arthur Peters (1922–1972), US American herpetologist. Today *Epicrionops petersi* Taylor, 1968

petersii: Peters + L. *-ii*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. (1) *Chthonerpeton petersii* Boulenger, 1882 “1861”. Today *Nectocaecilia petersii* (Boulenger, 1882). (2) *Geo-*

trypetes petersii Boulenger, 1895. In the synonymy of *Geotrypetes seraphini* (Duméril, 1859).

Phractamphibia: G. *phractus* (φρακτός), fenced, protected + L. Amphibia, a class of vertebrates; in turn from G. *amphibios* (ἀμφίβιος), living a double life. Phractamphibia Haeckel, 1866. [“...Panzerlurche...”]. In the synonymy of Gymnophiona.

Plesiophiona: G. *plesios* (πλησίος), nearby + G. *ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent + L. *-ona*, feminine suffix. Plesiophiona Dubois, Ohler & Pylon, 2021. [“...G: πλησίος (plesios), ‘near, close’; ὄφις (ophis), ‘snake’. This nomen is based on the same stem as the ordinal nomen Gymnophiona and the subordinal nomen Pseudophiona, and suggests the phylogenetic proximity of the species of this group with those of the latter. In the synonymy of Gymnophiona...”]. In the synonymy of Gymnophiona.

polyzona: G. *polys* (πολύς), several + G. *zona* (ζώνη), waistband, belt or girdle. *Caecilia polyzona* Fischer in Peters, 1880 „1879”. [“...Oben braungrau Kopf wenig heller, Ringfurchen schwarz; unten hellgrau...”]. Today *Oscacilia polyzona* (Fischer, 1880).

Potamotyphlus: G. *potamos* (ποταμός), river + G. *typhlos* (τυφλος), blind. *Potamotyphlus* Taylor, 1968. [?]. The same root in *Potomotyphlus* Taylor, 1968 (incorrect original spelling, corrected in errata distributed with original publication by publisher); also in *Potamotyphloidea* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Potamotyphlidae* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Potamotyphlinae* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Potamotyphlilae* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Potamotyphlini* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986,

praslini, Prasinia: F. Praslin, one of the islands of the Seychelles archipelago, in turn named in honor of César Gabriel de Choiseul, duc de Praslin (1712–1785), French military officer, diplomat, and statesman + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. (1) *Hypogeophis rostratus praslini* Parker, 1958. [“...collected on Praslin by the Percy Sladen Trust Expedition to the Indian Ocean in November 1905...”]. In the synonymy of *Hypogeophis rostratus* (Cuvier, 1829). (2) *Prasinia* Boulenger, 1909 [in the description of *P. cooperi*, the type-species of the genus, “...Two specimens from Praslin...”].

pressula: *L. pressula*, rather compressed. *Caecilia pressula* Taylor, 1968. [“...A species somewhat resembling *Caecilia tentaculata*, but with the body strongly compressed for most of its length...”]. In the synonymy of *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758.

pricei: Price + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Apodops pricei* Estes & Wake, 1972. Honoring Llewellyn Ivor Price (1905–1980), Brazilian paleontologist.

pricei: Price + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gymnopsis pricei* Dunn, 1944. Honoring Wilfred Devereux Price, author’s host at El Centro, Colombia. Today *Microcaecilia pricei* (Dunn, 1944).

primus: *L. primus*, first; 1st - (ORD, ‘in series’). *Gegeneophis primus* Kotharambath, Gower, Oommen & Wilkinson, 2012. [“...The specific epithet is in reference to the presence of only primary annuli...”).

proximus: *L. proximus*, nearest, closest, next. *Siphonops proximus* Cope, 1877. [“...This Caecilian resembles so much the *S. mexicanus* that I referred specimens of it to

that species in my Batrachia and Reptilia of Costa Rica...”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnopsis multiplicata* Peters, 1874.

pseudangularis: *G. pseudo* (ψευδής), false, untrue, mistaken + *L. angularis*, having angles or corners. *Ichthyophis pseudangularis* Taylor, 1965. [“...The name *pseudangularis* is from Greek, *pseudo*, false and Latin, *angulus*, angle...”].

pseudoangeli: *G. pseudo* (ψευδής), false, untrue, mistaken + [*Geotrypetes*] *angeli*, species due to Parker, 1936 (see this name). *Geotrypetes pseudoangeli* Taylor, 1968. [“...having about the same number of primary folds as *angeli*...”].

Pseudophydiens: *G. pseudo* (ψευδής), false, untrue, mistaken + *G. ophis* (ὄφις), snake, serpent. *Pseudophydiens* Blainville, 1816. [?]. Same root in *Pseudophidii* — Gray, 1825, *Pseudo-ophidia* — Blainville, 1835, *Pseudophidia* Gray, 1850, *Pseudophiona* — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

Pseudosiphonops: *G. pseudo* (ψευδής), false, untrue, mistaken + *L. Siphonops*, genus of gymnophiones due to Wagler, 1828 (see

this name). *Pseudosiphonops* Taylor, 1968. [...The type of the genus bears a superficial resemblance to *Siphonops annulatus* and *S. paulensis* and to certain forms of African *Geotrypetes*...]. Same root in *Pseudosiphonopiti* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Pseudosiphonopiti* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986. In the synonymy of *Mimosiphonops* Taylor, 1968.

***Pseudotyphlonectes*:** G. *pseudo* (ψευδής), false, untrue, mistaken + L. *Typhlonectes*, genus of gymnophiona due to Peters (1880) (see this name). *Pseudotyphlonectes* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986. [?]. Same root in *Pseudotyphlonectini* Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes* Peters, 1880.

***pti*:** Sc. *pti*, small. *Hypogeophis pti* Maddock, Wilkinson, Nussbaum & Gower, 2017. [...The specific epithet is in reference to the very small size of the species, one of the smallest of known caecilians. ‘Pti’ is a typical spelling in Seychellois Creole of the French petit, petite (small, in English)...].

***ptychodermis*:** G. *ptychos* (πτύχως), fold + G. *derma* (δέρμα), skin, hide. *Pseudosiphonops ptychodermis* Taylor, 1968. [...The two nuchal collars are distinct...]. In

the synonymy of *Mimosiphonops vermiculatus* Taylor, 1968.

***pulchraserrana*:** L. *pulchra*, pretty; beautiful + S. *serrana*, from the sierra. *Caecilia pulchraserrana* Acosta-Galvis, Torres & Pulido-Santacruz, 2019. [...The specific epithet is formed from the Latin *pulchra* (nominative feminine singular of *pulcher*), meaning beauty & the Spanish adjective *serrana* (feminine singular of *serrano*), from the sierra or serranía. This specific name refers to the type locality of the species: vereda La Belleza (beauty in English) in the western foothills of the Serranía de Los Yariquíes...].

rabei Rabe + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gymnopsis rabei* Roze & Solano, 1963. Unclear; probably Honoring some Marvin? Rabe, member of the botanical expedition to southern Venezuela (1961). Today *Microcaecilia rabei* (Roze & Solano, 1963).

***ramaswamii*:** Ramaswami + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gegeophis ramaswamii* Taylor, 1964. Honoring Ladapur Srinivas Ramaswami (1907–1987), Indian zoologist.

reinhardti: Reinhardt + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Mimosiphonops reinhardti* Wilkinson & Nussbaum, 1992. Honoring Johann Theodor Reinhardt (1816–1882), Danish zoologist.

Rhinatrema: G. *ris* (ῥίς), nose or snout of men and beasts + G. *-a* (-α), privative + G. *trema* (τρήμα), that which is created by drilling or piercing, aperture, hole. *Rhinatrema* Duméril & Bibron, 1841. [“... De ριν, nasus, nez; a privatif, et de τρήμα, foramen, trou, narines sans trous, ou nez non percé...”]. Same root in Rhinatrematidae Nussbaum, 1977, Rhinatrematoidea — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Rhinatrematoidea — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Rhinatremoidae — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986.

rochai: Rocha + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Microcaecilia rochai* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011. Honoring Reginaldo Augusto Trindade Rocha, a technician in the herpetological laboratory of the Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi.

ron: E. *Ron*, nickname of Ronald. *Rhinatrema ron* Wilkinson & Gower, 2010. Honoring Ronald Archie

Nussbaum (1942–), US American herpetologist.

rostrata: L. *rostratus*, having a beak, hooked, with a crooked point, beaked, with a curved front. *Coecilia rostrata* Cuvier, 1829. [“...à museau un peu plus pointu, sans bords blancs aux anneaux...”]. Today *Hypogeophis rostratus* (Cuvier, 1829).

Rubricaecilia: L. *rubrica*, red earth; red ocher + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Rubricaecilia* Evans & Sigogneau-Rusel, 2001. [“... From *rubrica* (L), meaning red earth, with reference to the Couches Rouges from which the assemblage comes, and caecilia...”].

russeli: Russel + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Idiocranium russeli* Parker, 1936. According to Beolens *et al.* (2013), the name honors W. M. Russell (1911–1979), US American-born British cryptozoologist.

sabogae: S. Saboga, island of the archipiélagos de las Perlas, Balboa district, Panamá; in turn, from Ch. *saboga*, rocky island + L. *-ae*, suffix indicating pertenance. *Caecilia sabogae* Barbour, 1906. [“...]

From Saboga Island...”]. In the synonymy of *Oscacilia ochrocephala* (Cope, 1866).

sartoria: L. *sartor*, patcher; mender; by extension, taylor. *Minascaecilia sartoria* Wake & Campbell, 1983. Honoring Edward Harrison Taylor (1889–1978), US American herpetologist. In the synonymy of *Gymnopsis syntrema* (Cope, 1866).

savagei: Savage + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Microcaecilia savagei* Donnelly & Wake, 2013. Honoring Jay Mathers Savage (1928–), US American herpetologist.

Schistometopum: G. *schistos* (σχιστός), branching, forked (although Parker probably meant to refer to *schizo*, σχίζω, split, divided) + G. *metopon* (μέτωπον), space between the eyes, brow, forehead. *Schistometopum* Parker, 1941. [“...Frontals small, widely separated medially...”].

Scolecormorphus: G. *scólecōs* (σκώληκος), worm + G. *morphi* (μορφή), form, shape, appearance. [?]. Same root in *Scolecormorphoidea* Taylor, 1969, *Scolecormorphoidea* — Lescure *Scolecormor-*

phus Boulenger, 1883. Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Scolecormorphoidea* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Scolecormorphoidea* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Scolecormorphinae* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986.

sechellensis: F. Se[y]chelles, island nation in the Indian Ocean, named after Jean Moreau de Séchelles (1690-1761), Louis XV’s Minister of Finance + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Dermophis sechellensis* Boulenger, 1911. [“...W. side of Mt. Seychellois, 1200 ft.... ”]. Today *Grandisonia sechellensis* (Boulenger, 1911).

sendenyu: ? Sendenyu, a village, Tseminyu sub-division, Kohima District, Nagaland, India. *Ichthyophis sendenyu* Kamei, Wilkinson, Gower & Biju, 2009. [“...Named after Sendenyu village, Nagaland state, where the type series was collected...”].

septentrionalis: L. *septentrionalis*, northern, north-; in northern hemisphere. *Dermophis septentrionalis* Taylor, 1968. [?]. In the synonymy of *Dermophis mexicanus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

seraphini: Seraphin + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of mascu-

line names and nouns. *Caecilia Seraphini* Duméril, 1859. Honoring Séraphin Braconnier (1812–1884), French “*garçon de laboratoire*” de la chaire des Reptiles et Poissons du Muséum de Paris. Today *Geotrypetes seraphini* (Duméril, 1859).

seshachari: Seshachar + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Gegeneophis seshachari* Ravichandran, Gower & Wilkinson, 2003. Honoring Bagepalli Ramachandrachar Seshachar (1908–1994), Indian zoologist.

shiv: E. *Shiv*, nickname of Shivnarine. *Rhinatrema shiv* Gower, Wilkinson, Sherratt & Kok, 2010. Honoring Shivnarine Chanderpaul (1974–), Guyanese cricketer

sikkimensis: Sa. Sikkim, an Indian state; in turn, from Sa. *Shijim*, crested + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis sikkimensis* Taylor, 1960. [“...Sikkium + ensis (Latin) = place or country...”].

simus: L. *simus*, flat-nosed, snub-nosed. *Siphonops simus* Cope, 1877. [“...muzzle wide, truncate, nostrils terminal...”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnopsis multiplicata* Peters, 1874.

singaporensis: E. Singapore, a sovereign island city-state; from Sanscrit *Simhapura*, lion city + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis singaporensis* Taylor, 1960. [“...Singapore + ensis = place, locality, country...”].

Siphonops: G. *siphon* (σίφων), a tube, pipe, siphon + G. *ops* (ὄψ), eye. *Siphonops* Wagler, 1828. [“...*truncus modice longus, omnino cylindraceus...*”]. Same root in Siphonopidae Bonaparte, 1850, Siphonopina Bonaparte, 1850, Siphonopinae — Dubois, 1984, Siphonopidae — Dubois, 1984, Siphonopoides — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Siphonopoida — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Siphonopoidae — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Siphonopinae — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Siphonopini — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Siphonopoidi — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Siphonopiti — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Siphonopina — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021, Siphonopinia — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021, Siphonopinoa — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021,.

spawlsi: Spawls + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Boulengerula spawlsi* Wilkinson, Malonza,

Campbell & Loader, 2017. Honoring Stephen Spawls (1953–), British herpetologist active in East Africa.

squalostoma: L. *squalus*, squali, kind of fish; shark + G. *stoma* (στόμα), mouth. *Caecilia squalostoma* Stutchbury, 1836 “1834”. [“...Muzzle prominent, with a slight protuberance situated about a line inferiorly and posteriorly to the nostrils...”]. Today *Herpele squalostoma* (Stutchbury, 1836).

Stegokrotaphia: G. *stego* (στέγος), roof + G. *krotaphos* (κρόταφος), side of the forehead. *Stegokrotaphia* Cannatella & Hillis, 1993. [“...based on the widespread occurrence of stegokrotaphy, or complete skull roofing, in this group...”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

subcaudalis : L. *sub-*, under + L. *caudalis*, referring to the tail (animal). *Epicrionops bicolor subcaudalis* Taylor, 1968. [“...subcaudal region brownish black...”].

subdermalis: L. *sub-*, under + G. *dermos* (δερμος), skin. *Caecilia subdermalis* Taylor, 1968. [“...subdermal scales in connective tissue...”].

subnigricans: L. *sub-*, less than + L. *nigricans*, to be blackish; *Caecilia nigricans* Boulenger, 1902. *Caecilia subnigricans* Dunn, 1942. [“...This form has fewer secondaries than *nigricans*...”].

subterminalis: L. *sub-*, less than + L. *terminalis*, terminal; marking a boundary; final. *Caecilia subterminalis* Taylor, 1968. [“...The “terminal” shield shorter and partly segmented...”].

subterrestris: L. *sub*, under + L. *terrestris*, terrestrial, earthly; living, operating on land (not sea). *Ichthyophis subterrestris* Taylor, 1960. [“...*Sub* (Latin) under + *terrestris* (Latin) = of the earth...”]. In the synonymy of *Uraeotyphlus bombayensis* (Taylor, 1960).

sumatranus: L. *sumatranus*, from Sumatra, one of the Sunda Islands of western Indonesia; in turn from Sa. सुवर्णद्वीपः, island of gold. *Ichthyophis sumatranus* Taylor, 1960. [“...Sumatra + *anus* (Latin) = place, location, country...”].

supachaii: Supachai + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis supachaii* Taylor, 1960. Honoring Supachai Vanijvadhana, Sec-

retary General of Chulalongkorn University.

supernumeraria: L. *supernumerarius*, exceeding the usual, stated, or prescribed number. *Microcaecilia supernumeraria* Taylor, 1969. [“... This form differs from the three other species recognized in this genus in having 40 more secondaries and 20 more primaries...”].

Sylvacaecilia: L. *sylva* (better *silva*), wood, forest, woodland + L. *Caecilia*, genus of caecilians due to Linnaeus, 1758 (see this name). *Sylvacaecilia* Wake, 1987. [“... From *sylva*, Gr. (sic), referring to the tropical deciduous forest habitat of these animals, and *caecilia*, L., in reference to the taxon...”].

syntremus: G. *syn* (συν), in company with, together with + G. *trema* (τρήμα), aperture, hole. *Siphonops syntremus* Cope, 1866. [“... This species differs from the four hitherto known, in the close approximation of the narial and tentacular openings...”]. Today *Gymnopsis syntrema* (Cope, 1866).

taitana: E. Taita [Hills], mountain range in the Taita-Taveta County, S. E. Kenya (from Sw. *teta*, defensive, quarrelsome, or aggressive) + L. *-ana*, of or pertaining to.

Boulengerula taitana Loveridge, 1935. [“...Mount Mbololo, Taita Mountains, Coast Province, Kenya Colony...”].

taprobanicensis: G. *Taprobana* (Ταπροβανᾶ), ancient Greek name for Sri Lanka + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Ichthyophis taprobanicensis* Taylor, 1969. [“...Ohiya Area, Ceylon...”]. In the synonymy of *Ichthyophis orthoplicatus* Taylor, 1965.

taylori: Taylor + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Microcaecilia taylori* Nussbaum & Hoogmoed, 1979. Honoring Edward Harrison Taylor (1889–1978), US American herpetologist.

tchabalmbaboensis: Fu. Tchabal Mbabo (or Tchabbal Mbabo), mountain range in Adamaoua Province, Cameroon (from Fu. *Tchabal*, high-altitude area with a flat relief, cold and windy climate, and grassy vegetation, which is typically used for grazing cattle, and Fu. *Mbabo*, a proper noun) + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Crotaphatrema tchabalmbaboensis* Lawson, 2000. [“...*Crotaphatrema tchabalmbaboensis* is named for the type locality, Mount Tchabal Mbabo, a remote, isolated highland consisting of a mosaic of

montane savanna, gallery forest and cloud forest. Tchabal Mbabo is located on the Adamaoua Plateau of Cameroon...”].

tejaswini: E. Tejaswini, river in Kasaragod District, Kerala, India (from Sa. तेजस्वनी, radiant, lustrous). *Gegeneophis tejaswini* Kotharambath, Wilkinson, Oommen & Gower, 2015. [“...The specific epithet is in reference to the type locality, which lies close to (less than 1 km north of) the Tejaswini (= Thejaswini) river. The origin of the river’s name is the Sanskrit word *tejas*, meaning spiritually splendid radiance....”].

tentaculata: L. *tentaculum* (feeler) + L. *-ata*, suffix added to nouns to form adjectives. *Caecilia tentaculata* Linnaeus, 1758. [? In the generic characterization, “...*Labium superius tentaculis 2...*”].

tenuissima: L. *tenuissima*, superlative of L. *tenuis*, thin, fine; delicate. *Caecilia tenuissima* Taylor, 1973. [“...A slender elongate species reaching a known length of 390 mm...”].

Teresomata: L. *teres*, rounded off, rounded, well-turned, round, smooth + G. *soma* (σῶμα), body.

Teresomata Wilkinson & Nussbaum, 2006. [“...These caecilians lack true tails and have, for the most part, more rounded (*teres*) ends to their bodies (*soma*) than rhinatrematids, ichthyophiids and uraeotyphlids...”]. In the synonymy of *Gymnophiona*.

thomense, thomensis: F. Thomé (in the original Portuguese, República Democrática de São Tomé e Príncipe), island nation off the Gulf of Guinea + L. *-ensis*, belonging to a place. *Siphonops thomensis* Bocage, 1873. [“...ils ont été rapportés de l’île Saint Thomé (côte occidentale d’Afrique)...”]. Today *Schistometopum thomense* (Bocage, 1873).

thompsoni: Thompson + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia thompsoni* Boulenger, 1902. Honoring Kay Thompson, collector of the holotype in Colombia; no further data available.

tremembe: P. *Tremembé*, an indigenous group that live in the state of Ceará, mainly in the municipality of Itarema; they have lost their native language and speak Portuguese. *Chthonerpeton tremembe* Maciel, Leite, Silva-Leite, Leite & Cascon, 2015. [“...a reference to the Tremembé ethnic group...”].

tricolor: *L. tricolor*, with three colors. *Ichthyophis glutinosus tricolor* Annandale, 1909. [“...I propose to call the form with the white ventral surface— var. *tricolor*...”]. Today *Ichthyophis tricolor* Annandale, 1909.

trombetas: *P. Trombetas* [Floresta Nacional (FLONA) Trombetas (0°57'45.97" S, 55°31'20.28" W), municipality of Óbidos, state of Pará, Brazil]. According to João de São José de Queirós da Silveira (1711–1764), bishop of Pará, referring to Trombetas, noted that “...êste foi o nome de um índio que dirigia a grande nação dos índios que vivem no seu sertão, chamado o principal Trombeta...” (Visita ao sertão, p. 212, cited by Cardoso, 1961¹). *Microcaecilia trombetas* Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011. [“...The name of the species refers to the type-locality...”].

Typhlonectes: *G. typhlos* (τυφλος), blind + *G. nektes* (νήκτης), swimmer. *Typhlonectes* Peters, 1880. [“...im Wasser lebend...”]. Same root in Typhlonectidae Taylor, 1968, Typhlonectoides — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Typhlonectoidae — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Typhlonectinae — Lescure,

Renous & Gasc, 1986, Typhlonectilae — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Typhlonectoidi — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Typhlonectini — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, Typhlonectina — Dubois, Ohler & Pyron, 2021.

uaiuai: *C. Uaiuai* or Wai-Wai, Carib-speaking native Americans. *Rhinatrema uaiuai* Maciel, Sampaio, Hoogmoed & Schneider, 2018. [“...honoring the Uaiuai Indians ...which include indigenous communities in southern Guyana and the southeastern part of the state of Roraima, the northeastern part of the state of Amazonas, and the northwestern part of the state of Pará in Brazil...”].

uluguruensis: *B. Uluguru* [Mountains], isolated mountain range in Eastern Tanzania (named after the Luguru people, inhabitants of the area) + *L. -ensis*, belonging to a place. (1) *Boulengerula uluguruensis* Barbour & Loveridge, 1928. [“...From Vituri, Uluguru Mountains, Tanganyika Territory...”]. (2) *Scolecormorphus uluguruensis* Barbour & Loveridge, 1928. [“...From Nyingwa, Uluguru Mountains, Tanganyika Territory...”].

1 Cardoso, L. A. 1961. Toponímia brasílica. Rio de Janeiro. Biblioteca do Exército. 476 p.

unicolor: *L. unicolor*, of one color; monochromatic. (1) *Bdel-*

lophis unicolor Boettger, 1913. [...vollkommen einfarbige, glänzend schwarze, wie lackiert erscheinende Färbung...]. In the synonymy of *Schistometopum gregorii* (Boulenger, 1895). (2) *Rhinatrema unicolor* Duméril, 1863. [...Teinte générale uniformément olivâtre, mais la tête et l'extrémité tout-à-fait terminale du tronc sont d'un jaune-verdâtre clair...]. Today *Microcaecilia unicolor* (Duméril, 1863).

Uraeotyphlus: *G. ouraios* (οὐραῖος), of the tail + *G. typhlos* (τυφλος), blind (frequent ending in caecilian names). *Uraeotyphlus* Peters, 1880. [...οὐραῖος, τυφλος...]. Same root in *Uraeotyphlinae* Nussbaum, 1979, *Uraeotyphlidae* — Duellman & Trueb, 1986, *Uraeotyphlilae* — Lescure, Renous & Gasc, 1986, *Uraeotyphlidinae* — Wollenberg & Measey, 2009.

venezuelense: Venezuela + L. *-ense*, belonging to a place. *Thyphlonectes compressicauda venezuelense* Fuhrmann, 1914. [...Quant à la provenance des exemplaires, ceux de Paris proviennent de Cayenne, ceux de Berlin du Venezuela (Caracas) et l'exemplaire de Hambourg de Maracaibo...]. In the synonymy of *Typhlonectes natans* (Fischer, 1880).

vermiculatus: L. *vermiculatus*, arranged to give an effect of wavy lines. *Mimosiphonops vermiculatus* Taylor, 1968. [?].

vermiformis: L. *vermiformis*, worm-shaped. *Caecilia vermiformis* Shaw in Gray, 1850. [?]. In the synonymy of *Caecilia gracilis* Shaw, 1802.

versatilis: L. *versatilis*, revolving; versatile. *Amphisbaena versatilis* Gray, 1850. *Nomen nudum*. In the synonymy of *Dermophis mexicanus* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841).

viscosa: L. *viscosus*, full of birdlime, sticky, viscous. *Coecilia viscosa* Latreille in Sonnini de Manoncourt & Latreille, 1801 “An. X”. [...La Cæcile visqueuse...]. In the synonymy of *Caecilia glutinosa* Linnaeus, 1758.

vittatus: L. *vittatus*, wearing or carrying a ritual ribbon or band. *Bdellophis vittatus* Boulenger, 1895. [...Bright yellow, with a broad black dorsal band...]. Today *Scolecophorus vittatus* (Boulenger, 1895).

viviparum: L. *viviparus*, of an animal that gives birth to developed live young, viviparous. *Chthonerpeton viviparum* Parker & Wett-

stein, 1929. [“...In *Chthonerpeton viviparum*, however, the eggs are retained within the oviducts...”].

volcani: L. *Volcan* + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia volcani* Taylor, 1969. Honoring Volcanus, Latin god of fire (etymology by the author).

weberi: Weber + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Ichthyophis weberi* Taylor, 1920. Honoring Max Wilhelm Carl Weber van Bosse (1852–1937), German-Dutch physician and zoologist.

wilkinsoni: Wilkinson + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Caecilia wilkinsoni* Fernández-Roldán & Lynch, 2023. Honoring Mark Wilkinson (1963–), Merit Researcher at the Natural History Museum in London, U. K.

yaigoje: S. [Parque Nacional Natural] Yaigoj´e [Apaporis]; in turn, from Ta. *Yaigojé*, place of the gods or sacred place. *Caecilia yaigoje* Fernández-Roldán, Medina-Rangel & Lynch, 2023. [“...This species is named after Parque Nacional Natural Yaigoj´e Apaporis, the first P. N. N. to be entirely desig-

nated as a protected area in response to the wishes and petitions of its native human inhabitants who believe in the conservation of the Amazon jungle and oppose any mining activities carried out in this region of Colombia...”].

youngorum: Young + L. *-orum*, genitive plural of the second declension. *Ichthyophis youngorum* Taylor, 1960. Honoring the family of Oliver Gordon Young (1927–2016), US American Baptist Missionary in Chiang Mai, Thailand.

zweifeli: Zweifel + L. *-i*, suffix indicating the genitive of masculine names and nouns. *Oscacilia zweifeli* Taylor, 1968. Honoring Richard George Zweifel (1926–2019), US American herpetologist.

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au texte, et par de nombreux exemples traduits; l'étymologie; les noms propres placés à leur ordre alphabétique; suivi d'une liste des racines mentionnées dans l'ouvrage, de tableaux sur le calendrier, les monnaies, les poids, et mesures, la numération des Grecs, et précédé d'une liste des auteurs et des ouvrages cités. Par M. A. Bailly (...). Librairie Hachette, Paris.

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